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Effect of temperature and molt stage on ion regulation of the Dungeness crab: characterisation of cation transporting ATPases

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*“Everything you can imagine,
nature has already created.”*

- Albert Einstein

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List of Abbreviations

A, B - postmolt
C –intermolt
D0- early premolt
D1-mid premolt
D2 –late premolt
D3 –late premolt
E – ecdysis
EJP - excitatory junction potential
ER - endoplasmic reticulum
Kcat - catalytic constant
Km - Michaelis–Menten constant
LDH - lactate dehydrogenase
M. magister – *Metacarcinus magister*
MIH - molt inhibiting hormone
NCX - Na⁺/Ca²⁺ exchanger
PMCA - plasma-membrane Ca²⁺-ATPase
SERCA - sacroplasmatic/endoplasmatic Ca²⁺-ATPase
SEM - standard error of the means
t₀ – before the incubation period
t₁₄ –14-day incubation period
WB - Western blotting
YOs - Y-organs
XO/SG - X-organ/sinus gland

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1 Summary

Crustaceans possess an exoskeleton, mostly consisting of calcium carbonate which stabilizes an animal body and protects them from predators. Periodically, crustaceans have to shed their old exoskeleton and synthesize a new one in order to grow, in a process called molting. This requires the transfer of massive quantities of ions through the body in a relatively short period of time, which is thought to be mediated by ion transporting ATPases like Na^+/K^+ -ATPase, Mg^{2+} -ATPase, PMCA and SERCA (cf. Wheatly et al. 2002). Temperature likely affects these enzymes however, it is essential for the ectothermic animals to maintain ion homeostasis within stable range besides changing temperatures (cf. Pörtner et al. 2005). Thus, the present thesis aimed at studying the effect of temperature on the molt-stage dependent function of essential ATPases in juvenile Dungeness crab, *Metacarcinus magister*.

Using samples from a preceding exposure experiment, maximal ATPase capacities of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase and an Mg^{2+} -ATPase were determined in the hepatopancreas of thermally acclimated crabs (10° , 15° and 20°C) which additionally differed by their molt stage (C, D0, D1, D2). For this purpose, specific assays for the respective ATPases were adapted and established for hepatopancreatic tissue, and several antibodies were tested for specific identification and quantification of the respective protein levels.

After adaption, the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity assay revealed reliable data, and Na^+/K^+ -ATPase capacity increased with proceeding molt cycle. Warm acclimated animals responded less than the cold-acclimated animals, demonstrating some level of metabolic cold compensation. The increments may support the calcification process by allowing elevated Ca^{2+} transport and further deposition in the exoskeleton and by establishing local osmotic gradients to support water influx across the epithelia to inflate the new exoskeleton.

Despite testing several assay buffers over a large range of Ca^{2+} concentrations no evidence for a clear Ca^{2+} dependent ATPase function could be drawn by use of thapsigargin, the specific inhibitor for the sacroplasmatic/endoplasmatic Ca^{2+} -ATPase (SERCA). Vanadate, the common inhibitor of P-Type ATPase provided only weak evidence for a Ca^{2+} dependent ATPase, most likely the plasma-membrane Ca^{2+} -ATPase (PMCA), but the varying data did not allow a clear assignment and quantification. Therefore, ATPase activity using the wide range P-type ATPase inhibitor vanadate in a Ca^{2+} -free buffer was determined. This Mg^{2+} dependent, vanadate sensitive ATPase provided no clear pattern besides a Q10 effect. Although this ATPase needs further characterization before final conclusions, the Mg^{2+} dependent activity was low in comparison to the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity, in line with the assumption that the uptake of Mg^{2+} by the animal is not that critical than a Na^+ gradient

facilitated Ca^{2+} uptake, due to the inward-directed Mg^{2+} gradient between seawater and body fluids.

A set of several heterologous antibodies was tested for the determination of the respective ATPases protein expression. Alongside the optimisation, it turned out that high amounts of several proteases in the hepatopancreas of *M. magister* caused reasonable degradation of proteins in the cell extracts. Finally, we identified a set of inhibitors (vanadate, PMSF and soy bean trypsin inhibitor), which stabilized the hepatopancreatic extracts in a way that quantification of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase protein expression was possible. Additionally, antibodies for PMCA and the mitochondrial F_1/F_0 -ATPase provided specific signals in the membrane fractions of at least one tissue, which may serve as a good starting point for further studies on ion-transporting ATPases in *M. magister*.

Similar to the functional capacities, Na^+/K^+ -ATPase protein expression increased with proceeding molt cycle, and warm acclimated animals responded less than the cold-acclimated animals. Correlation analyses of enzyme function, protein expression and mRNA expression, the later data provided by Dr. Wittmann from the same samples, were done to decipher underlying regulatory mechanisms. Overall, the correlation between mRNA and activity was quite strong, indicating a transcriptional control of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase function. The weaker correlations between mRNA vs. protein and protein vs. activity may be caused by some methodological concerns. Deviations from this general pattern could be observed for some stages indicating involvement of post-transcriptional mechanisms and protein modifications. As the specimen number of some stages were quite low, further studies are necessary to substantiate the observed trends.

Our findings about Na^+/K^+ -ATPase function are in line with previous findings for two other proteins involved in calcification and intermediated storage of Ca^{2+} , $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger, PMCA, also increasing in both concentration and activity with molt cycle and cold acclimation. It needs to be shown whether the reduced thermal responsiveness in the warmth may help to avoid overshoot of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase function and exhaustion of ATP at high and more frequent extreme temperatures which the crab *M. magister* may experience within its life cycle and additionally during summer. Despite, higher biological activity puts *M. magister* in a greater threat to predators and other environmental challenges to harden the new carapace timely.

Together this study provides some first evidence about molt stage and temperature dependent ATPase function and its regulation in the crab *M. magister*. A significant interaction of these two factors seem to exist, which may affect the ability of the crab to molt in a changing climate. Further research is needed especially for the Ca^{2+} dependent ATPases in order to understand the calcification abilities and possible danger for marine crabs in the light of climate change.

Key words: cation transporting ATPases, molt cycle, thermal acclimation, *Metacarcinus magister*, metabolic cold compensation

2 Introduction

2.1 Molt cycle in crustaceans

Crustaceans possess an exoskeleton, a structure which stabilizes an animal body and protects them from predators (Boßelmann et al., 2007). The exoskeleton is a biomineralized structure which consists of chitin and inorganic minerals, mostly calcium carbonate (Meldrum, 2003). Such composition gives an animal a mechanical strength, which serves as a protection but also gives flexibility for movements (Boßelmann et al., 2007). However, crustaceans have to shed their old exoskeleton periodically and synthesize a new one in order to grow, a process called molting (Hosamani, 2017). This requires a transfer of massive quantities of ions through the body in a relatively short period of time (Neufeld and Cameron, 1992).

The molt cycle takes nearly 120 days (Hosamani, 2017) and is divided into four main stages: intermolt (C), premolt (D0-3), ecdysis (E) and postmolt (A, B) (Chang and Mykles, 2011; Skinner, 1985). The majority of life, animals spend in the intermolt, during which they feed and reproduce (Ahearn et al., 2004). During premolt, ions from the exoskeleton are solubilized and transported via the integumentary epithelium to the blood and subsequently to cells, tissues and organs of temporary storage (Ahearn et al., 2004). The cycle culminates in the ecdysis, where the crabs shed their exoskeleton (Chang and Mykles, 2011). The newly synthesized cuticle takes up water to expand the new carapace and thereby the size of the animal (Hosamani, 2017; Chang and Mykles, 2011). After ecdysis, the body is very soft and the animal has no external protection, therefore there is great pressure to harden the new carapace as fast as possible (Neufeld and Cameron, 1992). In postmolt, ions are released from the organs of temporary storage and are once again transported throughout the hemolymph and the integumentary epithelium to harden the new exoskeleton (Ahearn et al., 2004).

All of these complex processes are regulated by several hormones. Two hormones have a predominant role in the initiation and coordination of the molting cycle, the molt inhibiting hormone (MIH) and ecdysteroids, which act in an oppositional manner to each other (Hosamani, 2017). Ecdysteroids are produced and secreted by a pair of molting glands, the Y-organs (YOs), which are located in the anterior cephalothorax (Abuhagr, 2014). Over the molting cycle a high fluctuation of the ecdysteroids hormones is observed (Chang and Bruce 1980; Chang and Mykles 2011). Therefore, molt stage can be determined by haemolymph ecdysteroid concentrations [10–40 pg μl^{-1} in intermolt (C), 50–160 pg μl^{-1} in early premolt (D0), 200–600 pg μl^{-1} in mid premolt (D1), ≥ 1000 pg μl^{-1} in late premolt (D2), and rapid decrease in ecdysteroids from D3 onwards (Wittmann et al., 2018).

Molt inhibiting hormone (MIH) is produced by the X-organ/sinus gland (XO/SG) complex located in the eyestalks of decapod crustaceans (Abuhagr et al., 2014). The Y-organs are activated to initiate increasing ecdysteroid concentrations in the hemolymph titers and therefore the conversion from the intermolt to the premolt stage. During postmolt and intermolt the Y-organ is in the basal state, resulting in a low ecdysteroid concentration in the hemolymph (Chang and Mykles, 2011). The reduction of MIH triggers the conversion to the activated state during premolt and thus an increase of the ecdysteroid levels occurs, reaching a peak at the end of the premolt state (Abuhagr et al., 2014). Few days before ecdysis, there is a large drop in the ecdysteroid levels, which serves as a trigger for shedding the exoskeleton (Abuhagr et al., 2014; Chang and Mykles, 2011; Wittmann et al., 2018).

2.2 Ions in crustaceans

Calcium is the most abundant cation in the crustacean's body and in the form of calcium carbonate makes up the majority of the exoskeleton (Greenaway, 1985). However, this structure is also built up of appreciable amounts of other ions notably magnesium, strontium and phosphorus (Greenaway, 1985). Magnesium and strontium are present largely as carbonates, while most of the phosphorus is present in organic forms such as phospholipids (Travis, 1963). During the molting cycle, ions must be transported through the hemolymph, therefore their concentration in the hemolymph differ from one stage to another. The possible fluctuations of the free ion concentrations in the hemolymph of crabs (here: *Callinectes sapidus*) are presented in **Table 1** (according to Towle and Mangum, 1985). The free sodium (Na^+), potassium (K^+) and chlorine (Cl^-) do not show significant changes from the intermolt (C) through ecdysis (E) to the postmolt stages (A 1-2, B1, B2). Instead, Mg^{+2} and Ca^{+2} fluctuated significantly with molt stage. The Ca^{+2} concentration in the hemolymph is coupled with the calcification of the cuticle during postmolt stages, as a decrease of the free Ca^{+2} in the postmolt stage A2 and B and an increase during the premolt stages could be observed (D1, D2, D3; Towle and Mangum, 1985). Calcium uptake by late postmolt integument (carapace plus epidermis) could be inhibited in crab *C. sapidus* by ouabain when applied to the epidermal side (Henry and Kormanik, 1985), suggesting an intimately role of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase for the transport of calcium across the epidermis. This ATPase is generating low intracellular sodium concentrations, which allows for the exchange of sodium and calcium across the apical membrane of the epidermal cell and subsequent movement of Ca^{+2} towards the cuticle (Towle and Mangum, 1985). The Na^+ -dependent Ca^{+2} efflux stoichiometry has been determined in several animal cells, including squid axon and barnacle muscle and is 3 Na^+ moving inward for 1 Ca^{2+} moving

outward (Godfraind-DeBecker and Godfraind, 1980). The decline in free Ca^{+2} in the hemolymph suggests that calcification of the cuticle is proceeding more rapidly than the release of Ca^{+2} from storage cells or uptake of Ca^{+2} from the medium. The Mg^{+2} concentration increases significantly after ecdysis (A1) by uptake from the medium, and declines by the postmolt stage B1, which reflects deposition of this ion in the cuticle as well (Sheets and Dendinger, 1983).

It is important to notice the ambient concentration of those ions in the seawater. Na^+ , K^+ and Cl^- fluctuations in the hemolymph stay within the range of the seawater concentration. Mg^{+2} concentration is well below ambient levels in the hemolymph, which simplifies its availability according to the animal needs. However, the Ca^{+2} demand of the animal exceeds the seawater concentration, which may cause constraints for calcification process. This suggests an important role for Ca^{+2} storage for crustaceans during the molt cycle, in comparison to the other ions.

Table 1 Free ion concentrations in the hemolymph of the blue crab *Callinectes sapidus* over the molt cycle. C-intermolt; D1-early premolt; D2- mid premolt; D3, D4- late premolt; E- ecdysis; A 1-2, B1, B2 – postmolt. * indicate significantly different from intermolt (C); $P < 0.05$; Student's *t*-test; Table modified according to Towle and Mangum, 1985.

Free ion concentration (mM ± SE)						
Stage	Na^+	K^+	Ca^{+2}	Mg^{+2}	Cl^-	N
C	434 ± 5	9.01 ± 0.14	9.03 ± 0.17	28.3 ± 0.7	511 ± 6	8
D1	407 ± 7	8.55 ± 0.16	9.24 ± 0.43	29.9 ± 1.1	498 ± 16	8
D2	396-407	8.43-8.63	9.15-10.7	31.6-32	512-536	2
D3	424 ± 13	9.19 ± 0.37	9.96 ± 0.48	29.3 ± 1.5	489 ± 20	6
D4	428 ± 5	8.78 ± 0.14	9.06 ± 0.52	33.8 ± 1.9*	543 ± 5	5
E						
A1	424 ± 9	8.94 ± 0.21	8.67 ± 0.30	35.3 ± 1.9*	532 ± 12	4
A2	445 ± 8	9.22 ± 0.20	7.57 ± 0.65*	32.5 ± 1.4*	532 ± 14	5
B1	403 ± 15	8.55 ± 0.21	6.68 ± 0.45*	28.0 ± 2.0	469 ± 18	8
B2	441 ± 5	9.22 ± 0.15	7.50 ± 0.47*	30.2 ± 1.1	532 ± 7	7
Sea water	420-433	8.50-9.10	8.38-8.96	43.8-47.4	517-541	9

The calcium content differs between animals. Its concentration in the body is linearly related to the size of the animal however, this might not be true for all crustaceans as the data are limited (Greenaway, 1985). The amount of calcium resorbed depends on several factors: the degree of storage of calcium practised by the species, the amount of resorption necessary to allow space for development of the new cuticle (Travis, 1955a) the amount of resorption necessary to allow the animal to extricate itself from the old exoskeleton (Drach,

1939) and the animal habitat. The most heavily calcified species are large marine decapods like *Cancer pagurus* (L.) but there is an overlap between the freshwater crayfish and the less calcified marine species (Greenaway, 1985).

In seawater, Ca^{2+} concentration reaches up to 10 mmol/L, while in freshwaters, calcium is far less available, with the concentration ranging from near zero to around 3 mmol/l (Greenaway, 1985). In both environments, food is an additional source for Ca^{2+} , but on land, it is the major source of this ion (Greenaway, 1985). Aquatic animals obtain ions mainly from the water, which is less problematic for the seawater species (Neufeld and Cameron, 1992). Thus, seawater species do not strongly depend on ion stores. Reserves however are very important for freshwater and terrestrial crustaceans (Roer and Dillaman, 1984). Freshwater species are in need to save ions from the old exoskeleton to later reuse them for deposition into the new structure (Neufeld and Cameron, 1992). Marine decapods lose most of their body calcium during ecdysis e.g. *Carcinus maenas* about 92%, while the supralittoral or terrestrial isopods *Ligia* and *Oniscus* lose only 25% and 40% of their body calcium, respectively (Graf, 1978). The majority of crustacean species are marine, but there are also freshwater and several groups of terrestrial species (Greenaway, 1985). The mechanism of restoration executes both, marine and freshwater animals, possibly, as it also allows them to save energy.

2.3 Ion transport mechanisms over the molt cycle in crustaceans

Calcium seems to be the most important ion regarding molting cycle and associated calcification. Therefore, the existing ion transport models presenting ion transport during the crustaceans molt cycle focus on this ion.

Crustaceans transepithelial Ca^{2+} flux is most active at stages surrounding exuviations (Wheatly et al., 2001). Intermolt crustaceans maintain stable Ca^{2+} balance (zero net flux), while premolt demineralization results in net efflux and postmolt mineralization requires uptake from external sources (Wheatly et al., 2002). The majority of the body Ca^{2+} (80%) is stored in the cuticle, and the remaining 20% is kept in the intra and extra- cellular fluid pools (Wheatly et al., 2002a). At the cellular level, 20% of Ca^{2+} is stored in the cytosol at low concentration (10^{-7} M), while the remaining 80% is stored in membrane-bound compartments at higher concentration (10^{-3} M), mainly the sarcoplasmic reticulum, which are able to exchange Ca^{2+} rapidly (Tumburu, 2010). There are several tissues with high Ca^{2+} transporting capacity: gills, antennal gland, hepatopancreas and hypodermis (Wheatly et al., 2001) however, the uptake level differ between the tissues. Lobster hepatopancreas for instance, had a 46-fold larger Ca^{2+} uptake capacity than the gill (Wheatly et al., 2002).

The current model of calcium transport in crustaceans depicts the plasma membrane proteins involved in transferring cations (redrawn from Wheatly et al., 2002a,b, **Figure 1**). This model bases on *in vitro* membrane vesicle studies performed on selected intermolt aquatic crustaceans. It is important to note that this transport system transport Ca^{2+} across the epithelial cell, both during intermolt, when Ca^{2+} requirements are low, and during the pre- and postmolt periods, when massive Ca^{2+} fluxes occur. Calcium transport requires coordination of transmembrane proteins such as channels, pumps, exchangers and binding proteins on apical, basolateral and internal membranes (Wheatly et al., 2002). Unidirectional apical to basolateral influx (postmolt gill and hepatopancreas; premolt hypodermis; intermolt antennal gland) is realized by passive movement of Ca^{2+} down its concentration gradient via $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger (NCX) or via diffusion through verapamil-sensitive Ca^{2+} channels (Wheatly et al., 2002; Ahearn et al., 2004). Transfer across the basolateral membrane requires a combination of both passive and active transport systems. Active basolateral efflux requires a vanadate-sensitive high-affinity, low-capacity calmodulin-dependent plasma membrane Ca^{2+} -ATPase (PMCA) and a low-affinity but high-capacity NCX that is fuelled by the Na^+/K^+ ATPase (Wheatly et al., 2001). PMCA seems to play a 'housekeeping' role in regulating intracellular calcium, while the NCX serves as the 'workhorse' responsible mainly for basolateral calcium efflux (Wheatly et al., 2001). During postmolt Ca^{2+} transport is mainly regulated via NCX, while in intermolt it is controlled by PMCA (Ahearn et al., 2004). Passive unidirectional basolateral to apical Ca^{2+} efflux (pre-molt hepatopancreas, post-molt hypodermis) involves a verapamil-sensitive Ca^{2+} channel (Wheatly et al., 2002). However, moving Ca^{2+} against its electrochemical gradient as for the transport across the basolateral membrane requires energy from the hydrolysis of ATP. This may be provided either directly in case of PMCA or indirectly as for NCX, which derives energy from the Na^+ gradient established by the Na^+/K^+ ATPase. Thus, the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase affect intracellular Ca^{2+} concentration (Pritchard et al., 2010). Basolateral PMCA- Ca^{2+} uptake is significantly greater in the presence of ATP, while vanadate, an inhibitor of P-type ATPases like the PMCA, reduced Ca^{2+} uptake significantly (Wheatly et al., 2002).

Water/Lumen
 $[Ca^{2+}]$ 0.5 mM FW
 9.5 mM SW

Hemolymph
 $[Ca^{2+}]$ 5 -12 mM

Figure 1 Model of the apical-to-basolateral transcellular Ca^{2+} transport and subcellular storage in crustacean epithelial cells (gills, antennal gland and hepatopancreas) based on isolated membrane vesicles. Pharmaceutical inhibitors are shown in parentheses. SR, sarcoplasmic reticulum; ER, endoplasmic reticulum; CaBP, calcium-binding protein; CaM, calmodulin; Mit, mitochondria; Vac, vacuole; FW, freshwater; SW, seawater; and RyR, ryanodine receptor. Figure modified according to Wheatly et al., 2002a,b.

Ca^{2+} might be stored in certain organelles such as mitochondria, lysosomes, and endoplasmic reticulum (ER). The ER acts as a Ca^{2+} depot, which possesses an active calcium ATPase (SERCA) (Hagedorn et al., 2003). SERCA facilitates Ca^{2+} uptake from the cytoplasm into the ER lumen by using the energy from ATP hydrolysis. It has a lower affinity for Ca^{2+} , but higher transport capacity compared to PMCA, commensurate with its relative abundance (Wheatly, 1999). Mitochondria participate in long-term Ca^{2+} storage and are considered as transient Ca^{2+} buffers, which are able to delay Ca^{2+} cytosolic diffusion after its release or entry (Wheatly et al., 2002). It has been suggested that mitochondrial Ca^{2+} storage increases when transepithelial Ca^{2+} flux is high (above 10^{-6} M) (Wheatly et al., 2002). Ca^{2+} can also be stored in granular form ($CaPO_4$ or $CaSO_4$) in membrane-clad concretion vacuoles or lysosomes (Becker et al., 1974). Epithelial lysosome membranes possess proteins, which can transport, certain divalent cations e.g. Ca^{2+} from the cell cytoplasm to the organelle interior, both in a passive and active way

(Chavez-Crooker et al., 2003a). Inside lysosomes they may form a solid precipitate that stays out of the cytoplasm (e.g. metals) or may be solubilized and transported back to the hemolymph when it is necessary (Ahearn et al., 2004).

As already mentioned moving ions against their electrochemical gradient requires energy mostly from the hydrolysis of ATP. The Na^+/K^+ -ATPase uses this energy to transport 3 Na^+ ions out of the cell and 2 K^+ ions into the cell. It is invariably composed of an α and β -subunit. The α -subunit is a protein with a molecular weight of about 110 kDa, and the catalytic site of the enzyme located on the α -subunit is responsible for the transport property (Chung and Lin, 2006). Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity is crucial in all cells for maintaining the ion homeostasis that drives solute transport including electrical signalling. This enzyme plays an important role in establishing local osmotic gradients to support water influx across the epithelia, which in case of molting inflate the new exoskeleton and produce transmembrane Na^+ gradients which drive epidermal Ca^{+2} efflux during postmolt calcification, respectively (Towle and Mangum, 1985). It therefore comprises a large proportion of cellular energy budget (20-70% of total ATP; Webster, 1981). An example of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity during the molt cycle was presented by Towle and Mangum (1985) (**Table 2**). Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity in gill and epidermis of the blue crab *Callinectes sapidus* increased significantly in late premolt (D4) and remained elevated throughout the postmolt stages (A1-2, B1, B2). The Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activities in the midgut were higher in postmolt stages, although not showing the degree of change as the gill or epidermis. According to the authors, the increases in Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity in late premolt and postmolt may be indicative for water uptake processes. At the level of the gill and epidermal cell, the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase may produce a transcellular gradient of Na^+ by exchanging this ion for K^+ . This increases the Na^+ concentration in the intercellular spaces, which are accessible to the hemolymph. Such an ionic gradient induces a local osmotic influx of water until reaching harmonized ionic concentrations between medium and hemolymph.

Table 2 Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase activities over the molt cycle in the blue crab *Callinectes sapidus* gill, epidermis and midgut. Number of animals given in parentheses (=individual assays, duplicates). Midgut values are given as means of duplicates (pooled tissues). C-intermolt; D1-early premolt; D2- mid premolt; D3-late premolt; D4 – late premolt; E- ecdysis; A 1-2, B1, B2 – postmolt stages. * indicate significantly different from intermolt (C); P<0.05; Student s *t*-test; Modified table according to Towle and Mangum (1985).

Na⁺ + K⁺ -ATPase activity (nanomoles ADP min⁻¹ mg protein⁻¹ ± SE)

Stage	Gill (1981)	Gill (1982)	Epidermis	Midgut
C	134 ± 8	201 ± 24	63 ± 12	98
D1	132 ± 20	176 ± 3	47 ± 10	79
D2	82 ± 21*	255 ± 40	68 ± 8	116
D3	147 ± 39	255 ± 46	89 ± 8	44
D4	218 ± 35*	321 ± 23*	100 ± 6	78-85
E				
A1-2	279 ± 22*	432 ± 21*	157 ± 23	116
B1	277 ± 31*	392 ± 25*	154 ± 16	140
B2	297 ± 44*	328 ± 23*	176 ± 29	144

2.4 Thermal compensation in crustaceans

Aquatic species are mostly strict ectotherms due to the fact that they lack anatomical and physiological means to maintain a thermal gradient between the body and the medium (Hochachka and Somero, 2002). Physiological performance, reflected mainly by growth and survival is optimal in a certain temperature range and define the thermal niche of species, and any temperature variation has a great influence on animal performance. However, many groups of ectotherms are able to change their physiological function to cope with an altered environment, which is referred as thermal compensation. Despite changes in temperature, it is essential for the animals to maintain the pH and ion homeostasis within stable range by modifications of the membrane permeability and adjustments of enzyme activities (Pörtner et al. 2005). As known as the Q10 effect, increasing temperatures elevate the rates of biological activity (Hochachka and Somero, 2002). The body temperature of ectothermic animals is dependent upon the temperature of the environment. Some ectotherms live in environments which provide near constant thermal conditions and allows these animals to keep stable body temperatures. Observations made on these thermally stable environments have shown limited tolerance of such ectotherms to sudden temperature changes (reviewed from Stephens and Atwood, 1982). By contrast, other environments have huge thermal fluctuations and such animals have to adapt to these changes in order to maintain functional integrity. In the crayfish *Astacus leptodactylus*, an ectotherm which lives in a temperature fluctuating environment, neuromuscular systems function over a wide

temperature range. Rapid thermal alterations provoke changes e.g. in membrane potential, changes in the amplitude, time course and facilitation of the junction potential (Harri and Florey, 1977). Interestingly responses of the animal are modified by prior acclimation of the *A. leptodactylus* to different temperatures (Harri and Florey, 1979). An example of such responses has been shown by Stephens and Atwood (1982). The walking legs of the shore crabs (*Pachygrapsus crassipes*) were removed from an animal, which has been acclimated to 12°C (cold acclimation) or 21 °C (warm acclimation) for at least 6 weeks, and the excitatory junction potential (EJP) was measured at several temperatures. In both cold- and warm-acclimated animals, increasing the temperature caused the EJP amplitude and time constant to increase initially to a maximum value, and then to decrease. Maximum values were obtained at temperatures close to the acclimation temperature, clearly showing the shift caused by the acclimation. The authors suggested that the decline caused by deviations in temperature is compensated by an increase in the amount of facilitation and in this way, the system is capable to retain its functional integrity over a wide thermal range.

Thermal compensation that maintains metabolic processes at rates, which are relatively constant even when temperature change, often results in higher metabolic rates measured at intermediate temperatures in cold acclimated animals compared to warm acclimated animals (Wakeling et al. 2000). An example of such pattern is given in Hochachka and Somero (2002), where higher enzyme lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity was measured at intermediate temperatures in cold adapted animals (Antarctic fish) than in warm adapted (tropical fish; **Figure 2**). It seems the overall outcome of adaptation to different temperatures has resulted in higher values in polar species than those from lower latitudes (Fields and Somero 1998), whereas concentrations of the enzymes are not modified to great extent (Hochachka and Somero 2002). It indicates that thermal compensation of enzyme activity may occur to maintain ion homeostasis in the cold.

Brain LDH Activity [Units/gWM]

Figure 2 Temperature compensation of lactate dehydrogenase activity (LDH) in the brain of Antarctic and tropical fishes. Enzymatic activity in homogenates of brain was measured at 10°C and extrapolated to the approximate habitat temperatures of the species (0° and 25°C for Antarctic and Tropicalfish respectively) using experimentally determined Q10 values. Data from Kawall et al., 2001; Figure redrawn from Hochachka and Somero, 2002.

In Young et al. (2006), the authors compared the effects of temperature on the neuronal conduction velocity propagation of a temperate isopod *Ligia oceanica*, and antarctic species, the amphipod *Paraceradocus gibber*. A complete thermal compensation was demonstrated for the conduction velocity of the antarctic species compared to its similar sized temperate relative (**Table 3**). When measured at the minimum antarctic environmental temperature (-1.8°C) conduction velocity in *P. gibber* was 24% faster than this in *L. oceanica*, when measured at the higher environmental minimum temperature for that species (+2°C). Even in the mid point of the temperature range (ca. at 10°C) for *L. oceanica*, and well above the maximum environmental temperature for *P. gibber*, the antarctic species maintained a faster conduction velocity.

Table 3 Conduction velocities of leg nerves measured at different temperatures in Antarctic species, *Paraceradocus gibber* and temperate species *Ligia oceanica*. Bold values indicate velocities at species-specific temperatures. -1.8°C and $+1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ represent the lower and upper environmental limits for the Antarctic species, and $+2.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, $+23^{\circ}\text{C}$ the corresponding limits for the temperate species. Table modified according to Young et al., (2006).

Conduction velocity [m s^{-1}]		
Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	<i>L. oceanica</i>	<i>P. gibber</i>
-1.8	0.24	0.71
1.5	0.48	0.85
2.0	0.54	0.88
10.0	1.24	1.27
23.0	2.11	1.78

2.5 Biochemical mechanisms of ATPases thermal compensation

As with all dynamic proteins, enzymes embedded in the plasma membrane such as the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase or PMCA, are especially susceptible to the cold, because of thermal effects on the lipid bilayer's viscosity and order. There are a variety of ways in which an animal could adapt to this thermal challenge. The simplest way would be to reduce the Na^+ leak and therefore an increase in pumping capacity would not be necessary (Schwarzbaum et al., 1991). A cell could also elevate the ion transport by increasing the number of pumps (Schwarzbaum et al., 1991) or the turnover rate of individual pumps. Another possibility could be homeoviscous adaptation of the membranes (Cossins et al., 1981; Raynard and Cossins, 1991; Schwarzbaum et al., 1992; Sinensky et al., 1979). Early studies using enzymes from related organisms that live in different thermal environments showed an increased catalytic efficiency for the cold orthologs (Dong and Somero, 2009; Fields and Somero, 1998; Hochachka and Somero, 2002; Kawall et al., 2002). The biochemical mechanisms behind this are modifications of the catalytic constant K_{cat} (turnover number of the enzyme), the Michaelis–Menten constant K_{m} (the concentration of substrate providing half of enzyme maximal activity) or both (Galarza-Muñoz et al., 2011). Another theory which describes how membrane systems adapt to temperature is homeoviscous adaptation. It states that the lipid membrane maintains a constant viscosity to compensate for temperature challenges (Sinensky, 1974). This is accomplished by changing the degree of saturation of the phospholipid acyl chains, the composition of the phospholipid head groups or the cholesterol content of the bilayer (Galarza-Muñoz et al., 2011). Because membrane bound enzymes operate within the viscous drag of the lipid bilayer, homeoviscous adaptation could help to mitigate

the effects of temperature on their activity. Cold adaptation requires a small number of amino acid substitutions that serve to reduce weak interactions within the enzyme, resulting in greater flexibility (Fields et al., 2006; Hochachka and Somero, 2002; Somero, 2004, Windisch et al. 2012). Active sites remain invariant, and most changes concern adjacent hinge regions, leading to greater mobility of the catalytic centre. It seems likely that membrane-bound enzymes undergo similar adaptations (Galarza-Muñoz et al., 2011). In Galarza-Muñoz et al. (2011), authors cloned Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α-subunits from an antarctic (*Pareledone* sp.; -1.8°C) and a temperate octopus (*Octopus bimaculatus*; ~18°C) and compared their turnover rates and temperature sensitivities. The primary sequences of the two pumps were found to be highly similar (97% identity) and at room temperature the maximum turnover rate of the antarctic pump was 25% higher than that of the temperate pump. Additionally, the antarctic pump exhibited a lower temperature sensitivity, leading to significantly higher relative activities at lower temperatures. Accordingly, reduced thermal sensitivity was suggested to be a common mechanism driving cold adaptation in the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase (Galarza-Muñoz et al., 2011).

The effect of the temperature acclimation on the non membrane ATPase – the SR Ca²⁺-ATPase has been investigated by Aho and Vornanen (1998). Thermal acclimation changed the activity of SR Ca²⁺ handling in both studied species the crucian carp *Carassius carassius* and rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss*. It was suggested that the reason for this might be some changes at the maximum rate of Ca²⁺ sequestration and also the Ca²⁺ affinity of the SR Ca²⁺-ATPase, as this would explain the differences between Ca²⁺-ATPase activities (measured at optimal Ca²⁺ concentration) and Ca²⁺ uptake rates (measured at a Ca²⁺ concentration close to the Km of the enzyme). Authors claimed that thermal acclimation may affect also passive Ca²⁺ leakage across SR membranes.

Mg²⁺-ATPase is localized in the plasma membrane and sarcoplasm (Veklich and Kosterin 2005). Its activity molecular mechanism is still very weak understood. Nozadze et al. (2015) conducted studies where the molecular mechanism of Mg-ATPase activity had been investigated. The Mg-ATPase activity was measured by the difference of inorganic phosphorus concentration in the medium where all conditions remained the same, except for the presence or absence of Mg²⁺. Different concentrations of Mg²⁺ were used (MgATP in the same concentration in all samples plus different concentrations of Mg²⁺ free). Concentrations were calculated by taking into account the MgATP complex dissociation constant (K = 0.0603 mM) (Iacimirsky and Gvasdovskaya 1972). In this studies, it has been demonstrated that Mg²⁺-ATPase is a multi-sited enzyme system whose functional unit is at least a dimer with 2 identical subunits. Its substrate is MgATP, which needs to be present in a low concentration because high concentration inhibits the enzyme.

Additionally, the free Mg^{2+} and free ATP ion modify the enzyme with a dual effect. The enzyme carries out Mg^{2+} transport at 1 Mg^{2+} :1 ATP stoichiometry. Mg^{2+} and ATP form MgATP complex. Therefore, „it is impossible to express the dependence of Mg-ATPase activity upon the substrate and modifiers concentrations as one variable function“. This makes kinetic analysis very difficult, as all ATPases need Mg^{2+} as an essential cofactor.

2.6 Dungeness crab *Metacarcinus magister*

Dungeness crabs *Metacarcinus magister* (Dana 1852), are an economically and ecologically important species distributed along the eastern Pacific coast from Alaska to Santa Barbara (CA, USA), with juveniles using the San Francisco Estuary as nursery habitat (Wild and Tasto, 1983). The various life stages of the Dungeness crab, *M. magister*, may experience broad environmental fluctuations in temperature, what might affect nearly all aspects of their physiological function (Brown and Terwilliger, 1999). The planctonic larval stages are found up to 150 km offshore (Lough, 1976; Hobbs et al., 1992), while metamorphosis from megalopa to juvenile, and also recruitment of juveniles takes place in coastal and estuarine waters (Brown and Terwilliger, 1999). The juvenile crabs inhabit the subtidal zone but they have been shown to also migrate to shallow and warmer intertidal mudflats in pursuit of prey (Stevens et al., 1984; Holsman et al., 2003). Therefore they are more likely to experience thermal stress even when they are foraging for food (McLean and Todgham, 2015). Adult *M. magister* occurs primarily in deeper estuarine and nearshore waters (Brown and Terwilliger, 1999).

Effects of temperature on survival and molt progression of the juvenile Dungeness crab has been studied by Wittmann et al. (2018). Over the 14-day incubation period (t_{14}) survival was 100% at 5°C and 15°C, 98% and 97% at 10°C and 20°C, respectively. At 30°C, all animals died within 24 h, at 25°C animals started dying after 3 days, with only 48% surviving after 7 days and 0% after 14 days. In terms of the molt progression, it increased with temperature (Wittmann et al., 2018). Among animals in the stage D0 at t_0 , individuals tested at 5°C did not progress in the moult cycle and remained at the same D0 stage within the 14 days. Crabs incubated at 10, 15 or 20°C did change the stage. At 10°C, 57% progressed to the stage D1, at 15°C, 31% progressed to D1 and almost half of the animals (46%) advanced to D2–3. At 20°C, 36% progressed to D1 and 36% progressed to D2–3 by the observation period. It indicates that molt interval decrease with temperature. Molt stage in this studies was determined after Drach and Tchernigofteff (1967) using illustrations of endites from Moriyasu and Mallet (1986), and also by the haemolymph ecdysteroid concentrations. Haemolymph ecdysteroid concentration was also determined

for animals in different molt stages: C, D0, D1 and D2 after 14 days of incubation at 10, 15 or 20°C and for all the individuals it varied by moult stage but not by temperature. Authors suggested two possible explanations for that. Low temporal resolution precluded detection of temperature-dependent differences in ecdysteroid titre or alternatively, similar ecdysteroid concentrations result from the active regulation of both biosynthesis and degradation/elimination of moulting hormone (Mykles, 2011).

In this study, hepatopancreas, tissue samples of the juvenile Dungeness crab, *Metacarcinus magister* were used for biochemical analyses. Hepatopancreas and the heart tissue samples were collected from animals in 2013 by Dr. Wittmann and already used in a previous study (Wittmann *et al.* 2018). The gill tissues were collected in 2014 by Dr. Wittmann. Crabs were caught at the end of June 2013 from the lower intertidal of Bodega Harbor, CA, USA. The water temperatures in the traps ranged from 14 to 22°C, while summer water temperatures in the intertidal of embayments and estuaries of Northern California and Oregon vary between 10 and 25°C (Brown and Terwilliger, 1999; Tasto, 1983). Animals at different molt stages were transported and incubated for 14 days in the recirculating incubation systems consisting of a water tank where individuals were kept separately. Each incubation system was kept at different, constant temperatures, from a temperature to which crabs were naturally exposed to (ca. 15°C) and temperatures, where changed growth and survival rates were expected (0-30°C). In regular intervals, as the molting cycle proceeded, individuals were sampled to obtain the hepatopancreas and the heart tissue. At the beginning (t_0) and the end of the experiment (t_{14}) haemolymph samples were collected from each individual to determine ecdysteroid concentration and therefore the molt stage. Tissue samples were frozen in liquid nitrogen and kept frozen at -80°C. Samples were subsequently transported to the AWI Bremerhaven (Germany).

2.7 Hypothesis and objectives

The aim of this research was to investigate the combined effect of temperature and molt stages on ion regulation of the Dungeness crab *Metacarcinus magister*. In more detail, I aimed at identifying and characterising relevant ion transporting ATPases, including Na^+/K^+ -ATPase, SERCA, PMCA and Mg^{2+} -ATPase, in the hepatopancreas *M. magister*. After optimisation of the test systems, maximal ATPase capacities of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase and an Mg^{2+} -dependent ATPase (in the thesis called Mg^{2+} -ATPase) were determined in the hepatopancreas of thermally acclimated crabs, which additionally differed by their molt stage. Heterologous antibodies were tested and used to quantify protein expression in the same tissue samples.

The **hypotheses** of this thesis are given as:

- 1) The capacity and expression of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase and other ion transporting ATPases increase towards the end of the molting cycle.
- 2) The ATPases (Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase and Mg²⁺ -ATPase) demonstrate thermal compensation to maintain ion homeostasis in the cold. Therefore, higher activities and protein expression are expected in cold acclimated animals (10°C) compared to the warm acclimated animals (20°C).

To provide evidence for the hypotheses a coupled optical enzyme assay were optimised for the specific ion transporting ATPases by using specific inhibitors in combination with selective ion containing buffers (ouabain: Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase; thapsigargin (+/- Ca²⁺) : SERCA: Vanadate (+/- Ca²⁺): PMCA and Mg²⁺ -ATPase). Due to the lack of a clear Ca²⁺ dependency of ATPase function only the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase and an Mg²⁺ -ATPase were finally quantified in differently thermally acclimated Dungeness crabs from different molt stages. The assay temperature was varied to characterise the thermal sensitivity of the respective enzymes in the different treatment groups.

The protein expression of the related transport ATPases was determined by immunological methods (Western blotting) to provide evidence for the molecular regulation of the enzyme function. To do so, seven heterologous antibodies raised against Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase, PMCA, F₁/F₀-ATPase were tested for the first time in different tissue of *M. magister* (hepatopancreas, gills, heart). Finally, antibodies for Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase, PMCA, F₁/F₀-ATPase provided specific signals in the membrane fractions of at least one tissue. In the end, protein expression was determined for the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase in the same samples as for the enzyme capacities.

Involved mechanisms of regulation were investigated by comparing the enzyme capacities and protein expression by means of correlation analyses. Similar, mRNA expression obtained from Dr. Wittmann (unpublished) from the same tissue samples were related to the respective enzyme functions.

The study provided some first evidence about molt stage and temperature dependent ATPase function and its regulation in *M. magister*. Moreover, a significant interaction of these two factors seem to exist, which may affect the ability of the crab to molt in a changing climate.

3 Material

3.1 Animals

In this study, hepatopancreas, tissue samples of the juvenile Dungeness crab, *Metacarcinus magister* (Dana 1852) were used for biochemical analyses. Hepatopancreas and the heart tissue samples were collected from animals in 2013 by Dr. Wittmann and already used in a previous study (Wittmann et al., 2018). The gill tissues were also collected by Dr. Wittmann in 2014. Crabs were caught at the end of June 2013 from the lower intertidal of Bodega Harbor, CA, USA. When crabs were collected after one tidal cycle (ca. 24 h), water temperatures in the traps ranged from 14 to 22°C. Animals at different molt stages (12, 19 or 26 days postmolt) were transported and incubated for 14 days in the recirculating incubation systems consisting of a water tank of 200–500 litres, where individuals were kept separately in glass jars of 470 ml. Each incubation system was kept at different, constant temperatures, from a temperature to which crabs were naturally exposed to (ca. 15°C) and temperatures, where changed growth and survival rates were expected (0-30°C). In regular intervals, as the molting cycle proceeded, individuals were sampled to obtain the hepatopancreas and the heart tissue. At the beginning (t₀) and the end of the experiment (t₁₄) haemolymph samples were collected from each individual to determine ecdysteroid concentration and therefore the molt stage. Tissue samples were frozen in liquid nitrogen and kept frozen at -80°C. Samples were subsequently transported to the AWI Bremerhaven (Germany).

3.2 Agents and solutions

The chemicals used in this thesis are listed in **Table 4**. Antibodies and applied dilutions used for Western blotting (WB) analysis are listed in **Table 5**. All buffers, solutions and gels listed in **Table 6**, were made with Millipore water. Kits and protein ladders are listed in **Table 7**.

Table 4 Chemicals

Name	Company
1-Butanol	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Aceticacid (CH ₃ COOH)	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Acrylamide	National Diagnostics (Atlanta, USA)
Adenosine 5'-triphosphate disodium salt hydrate (Na ₂ -ATP)	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)

β - NADH- Na_2	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Ammonium persulfate (APS)	Bio-Rad Laboratories (München, Germany)
Bromophenol blue	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Bovine serum albumin (BSA)	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250	Bio-Rad Laboratories (München, Germany)
Desoxycholic acid	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
Ethanol	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Ethylene diamine tetraacetic acid disodium salt dihydrate ($\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$)	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Ethylene glycol-bis (2-aminoethylether)-N,N,N',N'-tetraaceticacid (EGTA)	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Glycerol	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Glycine	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Hydrogen chloride (HCl)	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Imidazole	Honeywell Fluka (by: Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Ionophore A23187	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
K- Phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP)	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Magnesium chloride (MgCl_2)	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)

Methanol	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Milk powder non-fat skimmed	Biomol GmbH (Hamburg, Germany)
Orthovanadate	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
Ouabain	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
Phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF)	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
Polysorbate 20 (Tween 20)	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Potassium chloride (KCl)	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Protease Inhibitor cocktail	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
Pyruvate Kinase/Lactic Dehydrogenase (PK/LDH-Mix)	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
Sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO ₃)	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Sodium carbonate (Na ₂ CO ₃)	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Sodium chloride (NaCl)	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS)	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Soybean trypsin inhibitor	Sigma Aldrich (now: Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany))
Sucrose	Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG (Karlsruhe, Germany)
Tetramethylethylenediamine (TEMED)	AppliChem GmbH (Darmstadt, Germany)
Trichloroacetic acid (TCA)	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany)
Tris (hydroxymethyl) aminomethane (Tris)	Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG (Karlsruhe, Germany)

Table 5 Antibodies

Antibody	Dilution	Species	Host	Supplier
Anti Ca ²⁺ pump PMCA [5F10]	1:1000	Chicken	Mouse	Abcam, Cambridge, UK
Anti Ca ²⁺ pump (CaF2 serum)	1:100	Chicken	Mouse	DSHB, Iowa, USA
F ₁ F ₀ -ATP synthase α	1:5000	Bovine	Mouse	Abcam, Cambridge, UK
H300 (Na ⁺ /K ⁺ -ATPase α)	1:5000	Human	Rabbit	Santa Cruz biotechnology
Anti-Hsp70	1:5000	Human	Mouse	ThermoFisher, Rockford,USA
Na ⁺ /K ⁺ ATPase α 5	1:100	Chicken	Mouse	DSHB, Iowa, USA
Na ⁺ /K ⁺ ATPase α 6	1:5000	Chicken	Mouse	DSHB, Iowa, USA
ECL Anti Mouse IgG Horseradish Peroxidase linked whole Ab	1:50000	Mouse	Sheep	GE Healthcare UK
ECL Anti Rabbit IgG Horseradish Peroxidase linked whole Ab	1:20000	Rabbit	Donkey	GE Healthcare UK

Table 6 Solutions, buffers and electrophoresis gels

Name	Composition
β - NADH- Na ₂	0.01M β -NADH- Na ₂ , 50 mM Imidazole/HCl (pH 7.4)
Acrylamide solution 30 %	30 % (w/v) acrylamide/bis (37.5:1)
APS	100 mg/mL APS in water
NaK ATPase assay buffer	100 mM imidazole (pH 7.4), 80 mM NaCl, 20 mM KCl, 5 mM MgCl ₂ , 0,5 mM ionophore A23187, 5 mM Na ₂ -ATP, 2 mM PEP, 1mM PK/LDH-Mix, 0.24 mM β -NADH-Na ₂

Ca (-) ATPase assay buffer (Mg ATPase determination)	25 mM imidazole (pH 7.4), 50 mM KCl, 2,5 mM MgCl ₂ , 100 μM EGTA, 0,5 mM ionophore A23187, 5 mM Na ₂ -ATP, 2 mM PEP, 1mM PK/LDH-Mix, 0.24 mM β-NADH-Na ₂
Ca (+) ATPase assay buffer	25 mM imidazole (pH 7.4), 50 mM KCl, 2,5 mM MgCl ₂ , 100 μM EGTA, CaCl ₂ at several concentrations (50 μM, 100 μM, 250 μM, 500 μM, 5 mM), 0,5 mM ionophore A23187, 5 mM Na ₂ -ATP, 2 mM PEP, 1 mM PK/LDH-Mix, 0.24 mM β-NADH-Na ₂
Blocking buffer	5 % (w/v) skimmed milk powder in 1-fold TBS-T
BSA Protein standard	BSA (in a volume between 1 and 10 μl) in 0.9% saline
Bradford reagent	100 mg/L Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250, dissolved in 5% (v/v) ethanol, 8.5 % (v/v) phosphoric acid
Desoxycholic acid	5% (w/v) Na-desoxycholate in water
Destaining solution	5% (v/v) Methanol, 7,5% (v/v) Acetic acid
Electrophoresis running buffer	25 mM Tris, 192 mM glycine, 0.1 % (w/v) SDS
Extraction Buffer NaK	50 mM imidazole (pH 7.4), 250 mM sucrose, 1 mM EDTA, 5 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 0.1 % (v/v) desoxycholic acid, 2 % (v/v) protease inhibitor (Sigma)
Extraction buffer P+ (with additional protease inhibitors)	50 mM imidazole (pH 7.4), 250 mM sucrose, 1 mM EDTA, 5 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 0.1 % (v/v) desoxycholic acid, 2 % (v/v) protease inhibitor (Sigma), 0,5 mM PMSF, 1mM vanadate
K- Phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP)	0.1 M K- Phosphoenolpyruvate in water
Ouabain	0.3 M Ouabain in DMSO
PMSF stock (1000fold)	20 mg/ml PMSF in Methanol
SDS sample buffer (3fold)	62.5 mM Tris/HCl (pH 6.8), 2 % (v/v) SDS, 0.005 % (w/v) bromphenol blue, 10 % (v/v) glycerine (87 %), 5 % (v/v) β-mercaptoethanol (99 %)
Separating gel	0.375 M Tris/HCl (pH 8.8), 0.1 % (v/v) SDS, 10% Acrylamide/bis Acrylamide (37.5:1), 1 mg/ml APS, 1 μl/ml TEMED
Stacking gel	0.125 M Tris/HCl (pH 6.8), 0.1 % (v/v) SDS, 4% Acrylamide/bis Acrylamide (37.5:1), 1 mg/ml APS, 1 μl/ml TEMED
Staining solution	3mM Coomassie Blue, 45,4 % (v/v) Methanol, 9,2% (v/v) Acetic acid, 0,6 M TCA
TBS-T (1fold)	50 mM Tris/HCl (pH 7.4), 0.9 % (w/v) NaCl, 0.1 % (v/v) Tween 20
Transfer buffer (pH 9.5-9.9)	10 mM NaHCO ₃ , 3 mM Na ₂ CO ₃ , 20 % (v/v) Methanol, 0.025 % (v/v) SDS (10%)

Vanadate stock solution 60 mM Orthovanadate, adjusted with HCl to pH 10 after several rounds of heating

Table 7 Kits and protein ladders

Name	Company
Amersham ECL Western Blotting Detection Kit	GE Healthcare (Freiburg, Germany)
Precellys CKMix Tissue Homogenizing Lysing Kit	Bertin Instruments (Montigny-le-Bretonneux, France)
Precision Plus Protein Standards All Blue Catalog #161-0373	Bio-Rad Laboratories (München, Germany)
Precision Plus Protein Standards Dual Color Single Unit Catalog #161-0374	Bio-Rad Laboratories (München, Germany)

3.3 Laboratory material and equipment

All laboratory materials, equipment and software used in this thesis are listed in **Table 8** and **Table 9**.

Table 8 Laboratory material

Name	Company
Disposable cuvettes (1ml)	Brand GmbH (Wertheim, Germany)
Electrophoresis System Mini-Protean 3 Cell	Bio-Rad Laboratories (München, Germany)
Eppendorfs	Eppendorf AG (Hamburg, Germany)
Falcon tubes (15 mL and 50 mL)	Corning GmbH (Kaiserslautern, Germany)
Filter paper Bio-Dot SF	Bio-Rad Laboratories (München, Germany)
Immun-Blot PVDF Membrane	Bio-Rad Laboratories (München, Germany)
Nitrocellulose membrane Trans-Blot	Bio-Rad Laboratories (München, Germany)
Trans-blot cell	Bio-Rad Laboratories (München, Germany)
Ultracentrifuge tubes (13x51mm, 3.0mL)	Beckman (CA, USA)

Table 9 Software and equipment

Name	Company
AIDA Image Analyzer software, Version 3.52	Raytest (Straubenhardt, Germany)
Analytical balance Satorius LA620S	Wagetechnik Nord GmbH, (Hohenlockstedt, Germany)

CCD-camera LAS-1000	Fujifilm (Tokio, Japan)
Cooling system	Haake F6 (Karlsruhe, Germany)
5417 D Centrifuge	Eppendorf AG (Hamburg, Germany)
Welding machine	Severin Elektrogeräte GmbH (Sundern, Germany)
Precellys 24 Tissue Homogenizer	Bertin Instruments (Montigny-le-Bretonneux, France)
Roto-Shake Genie	Scientific Industries Inc. (NY, USA)
SigmaPlot, Version 12.0	Systat Software (San Jose, California, U. S.)
SigmaStat, Version 3.5	Systat Software (San Jose, California, U. S.)
Spectrophotometer	Analytic Jena Specord S600 (Jena, Germany)
Spectrophotometer (protein determination)	Pharmacia Biotech LKB Biochrom 4060, (Cambridge, England)
Thermomixer comfort	Eppendorf AG (Hamburg, Germany)
Ultracentrifuge Optima Max-xp	Beckman Coulter (CA, USA)
WinASPECT Software Analytik	Jena AG (Jena, Germany)

4 Methods

4.1 Protein extraction

Proteins for measuring the maximum enzyme activity were extracted from frozen hepatopancreas tissue of the crab *M. magister* by homogenisation using the Precellys 24 Tissue Homogenizer (Bertin Instruments, France). Samples were homogenized in 10 μ l ice-cold extraction buffer per mg tissue wet weight at 6,000 rpm for 20 s. Subsequently, extracts were centrifuged at 1,000 \times g for 10 min at 4°C to remove cell debris and to obtain crude extract.

For electrophoresis and western blotting the crude extract, cytosolic fraction and membrane fraction of hepatopancreas, heart (*M. magister* collected in 2013 by Dr. Astrid Wittmann) and gill (*M. magister* collected in 2014 by Dr. Wittmann) were used. The crude extract was obtained as described above, except the fact that the extraction buffer optimized for additional inhibitors: (i) PMSF, (ii) vanadate and (iii) soy bean trypsin inhibitor (see results). To separate the cytosolic and membrane fractions the crude extract was placed into an ultracentrifuge tube (Beckman, USA) and centrifugated with an Ultracentrifuge Optima Max-xp (Beckman Coulter, USA) at the speed 60,000 rpm (\pm 195,000 g) in 4°C for 30 min. As the sample tubes need to be exactly balanced (\pm 0.01 g.), an extra volume of the extraction buffer was used for this. The supernatant (cytosolic fraction) was carefully transferred to a labelled reaction tube and stored on ice. Subsequently, all liquid residuals were carefully removed from the inner wall of the centrifuge tube with filter paper without touching the pellet. The pellet (membrane fraction), was resolved in a volume of 2 μ l or 4 μ l extraction buffer per 1 mg wet weight in two steps. Firstly the pellet was resolved with about half the amount of extraction buffer by rinsing the tube wall with a pipette and transferring it into a labelled tube. The rest of the buffer was then used to clean the ultracentrifuge tube completely and to transfer the rest to the labelled tube. Finally, the membrane fraction was completely homogenized by repeated pipetting.

In order to linearize proteins for further electrophoresis/western blotting, the crude extract, cytosolic fraction and membrane fraction were mixed with SDS sample buffer (2:1) and stored in the freezer until use.

4.2 Measurements of ATPase activities in the hepatopancreas

4.2.1 Optimisation

For measuring ATPases activity in the hepatopancreas of the crab *M. magister* assays needed to be optimized. Several assay buffers were tested combined with different inhibitors to find the maximal inhibition and inhibitor specific activity. The optimisation was done

at 20°C assay temperature. To determine Ca²⁺-ATPase activity several Ca ATPase assay buffers (Saborido et al., 1999) (with different Ca concentrations: 0 μM, 50 μM, 100 μM, 250 μM, 500 μM, 5 mM) were tested with both the SERCA specific inhibitor –thapsigargin (Lyttonsg et al., 1991) and the wide range P-type ATPase inhibitor vanadate (Csermely et al., 1985a) for the detection of the plasma membrane Ca²⁺-ATPase (PMCA). As no clear evidence for Ca²⁺-ATPase (either SERCA or PMCA) could be drawn from these tests, we decided to measure general ATPase activity using the wide range P-type ATPase inhibitor vanadate in the Ca (-) ATPase assay buffer (0 μM Ca²⁺) and we assigned this as Mg²⁺- dependent ATPase activity, further called in this thesis as Mg²⁺-ATPase (see 5.1.1). The Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity was successfully determined with the commonly used NaK ATPase assay buffer (Deigweiher et al. 2008) combined with Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase specific inhibitor – ouabain (Pchejetski et al., 2003) and in this combination it was measured in the further analyses.

4.2.2 Final conditions

The Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase and Mg²⁺- ATPase activity was determined using the formation of ADP and Pi from ATP in a coupled optical-enzymatic assay in the following manner:

The turnover of the substrate ATP is coupled to the oxidation of NADH to NAD⁺. The measurement bases on the fact that the reduced forms of the cofactor has an absorption maximum at 340 nm, while the oxidized form absorbs no light at this wavelength. Thus, any dehydrogenase reaction can be followed by determination of the extinction at 340 nm. As 1 mole of ATP consumed equals exactly 1 mole of NADH oxidized, the absorbance is directly proportional to the substrate turnover. To measure the specific enzyme activity of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase and Mg²⁺-ATPase the difference of total ATPase enzyme activity and selective inhibitor-sensitive activity were determined in their specific assay buffer. Ouabain was used to inhibit the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity and vanadate was used as an inhibitor for the Mg²⁺-ATPase. Both enzymes were measured in duplicates in the same crude extract samples. The enzyme activity measurements were performed using

a thermostatic spectrophotometer (Analytic Jena Specord S600, Jena, Germany) at 340 nm and 3 assay temperatures: 10°C, 15°C and 20°C. Respective inhibitors (1.2 mM ouabain, 25.3 µM vanadate or 0.56 M DMSO as a control for the solvent used for the inhibitors) in a volume of 2 µl was attached to the bottom of the disposable cuvette (200 µl UV-Cuvette, Brand GmbH, Wertheim, Germany). Subsequently, a master mix containing all components besides the sample was added and mixed by pipetting. After the photometer was equilibrated to the respective temperature (10°C, 15°C or 20°C) cuvettes were placed into the photometer block and equilibrated. As blank water was used. After about 1 min of prerun, 4 µl of the sample crude extract was added to each cuvette (total volume 204 µl) and mixed with a stirring rod (separate for each cuvette). The activity of ATPase was followed by the decrease in extinction at 340 nm over a total of 20 min. The slope $\Delta E/\Delta t$ was determined in the linear range of absorbance. Tissue specific enzyme activity A per fresh weight [$\mu\text{mol}/(\text{h}\cdot\text{g})\text{FW}$] was calculated as:

$$A \text{ fresh weight} = \frac{\Delta E}{\Delta t * d * \epsilon} * \frac{V \text{ cuvette}}{V \text{ sample}} * \frac{V \text{ crude extract}}{m \text{ wet weight}} * 60$$

where $\Delta E/\Delta t$ is the maximum slope after adding the sample in minutes, d is the thickness of the cuvette (1cm), ϵ is the extinction coefficient ($6.31 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$), $V \text{ cuvette}$ is the total volume of the cuvette in µL, $V \text{ sample}$ is the volume of the sample in µL, $V \text{ crude extract}$ is the volume of the extraction buffer in mL and $m \text{ wet weight}$ is the mass of the tissue wet weight of the crude extract in g. The specific activity was calculated as the difference between the total ATPase activity (TA) and the inhibited activity by either ouabain (OA) or vanadate (VA).

$$TA - OA = \text{Na}^+/\text{K}^+\text{-ATPase}$$

$$TA - VA = \text{Mg}^{2+}\text{-ATPase}$$

4.3 Protein expression of ATPases

4.3.1 Optimisation

The only difference between the optimization and the proper protein expression experiments is the type of used antibody. The rest of the process follows as described below (see 4.3.2; 4.3.3; 4.3.4). The validation of antibodies for Western analyses is described in detail in the Results -see 5.2.1.

4.3.2 Denatured Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE)

Proteins were separated by electrophoresis with the use of the Electrophoresis System (Mini-Protean 3 Cell, Bio-Rad Laboratories, USA; gel size: 8 cm (W)x 7.3 cm (H)) using a 10 % separating gel overlaid by a 4 % stacking gel, according to Laemmli (1970). Apart from the protein samples (mixed with 3-fold SDS sample buffer), a pre-stained protein standard (Bio-Rad Laboratories) was loaded on every gel in a volume of 7 μ l. The electrophoresis was performed at 200 V for ca. 45 min.

4.3.3 Electrotransfer of proteins

The gels with separated proteins were submerged in fresh transfer buffer and equilibrated for 15min. Similar nitrocellulose membranes were equilibrated for 30 min. Afterwards, proteins from the gel were transferred onto the nitrocellulose membranes (Bio-Rad Laboratories) at 35 V at 4°C for ca. 3 h using a tank blotting system (Trans-blot cell, Bio-Rad Laboratories, USA) with 4 L of transfer buffer equipped with a cooling coil connected to a cooling system (Haake F6) and adjusted to 4°C.

4.3.4 Western blotting analysis

The expression of proteins was quantified in different fractions/extracts by means of electrophoretic separation and following Western blotting.

The membrane was incubated for 1 h in blocking buffer at RT for saturating non-specific binding of proteins. Subsequently, the membrane was enclosed in a small foil bag together with primary antibodies (Na⁺/K⁺ATPase α 5 in a dilution 1:100 or Anti Ca²⁺pump PMCA [5F10] in a dilution 1:1000) diluted in 5 mL blocking buffer and incubated overnight at 4°C on a rotation shaker (Roto-Shake Genie, Scientific Industries Inc.). The next day, the membrane was washed 4x 10 min with TBS-T to remove unbound primary antibodies and treated with secondary antibodies (ECL Anti Mouse IgG Horseradish Peroxidase linked whole Ab) diluted in blocking buffer (1:50 000) for 1 h at RT. After another washing (4x 10 min with TBS-T) bound antibodies were detected with the ECL Advance Western blotting detection reagent (GE Healthcare, Munich, Germany) and recorded by a cooled charge-coupled device camera (LAS-1000: Fuji, Tokyo, Japan). Intensities of the protein bands were calculated using the AIDA Image Analyzer software (version 3.52, Raytest, Straubenhardt, Germany).

4.4 Protein content determination

The protein determination in tissue extracts and cellular fractions was done according to Bradford (1976). This method makes use of the change in the absorption of the dye "Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250" upon binding to proteins. This binding shifts the absorption maximum of the acidic dye solution from 460 nm to 595 nm. The development of the colour is linear over a 10-fold concentration range so that it can be used for the quantification of proteins.

All dilutions of the samples were retained in 0.9% saline solution (NaCl in water). Samples of the BSA protein standard at a volume between 1 and 10 μl (equals 1 to 10 μg protein) were pipetted to a 1ml cuvette together with 1 ml of Bradford solution. Samples were mixed carefully by inverting the cuvettes several times while closing them with parafilm-covered fingers. After 10 min extinction was measured at 595 nm with a spectrophotometer (Pharmacia Biotech LKB Biochrom 4060, Cambridge, England). Samples of the crab *M. magister* hepatopancreas crude extracts and membrane fractions were diluted 5fold with 0,9% saline to be in the range of the calibration curve. Subsequently, 5 μl of the dilution was pipetted to a cuvette and mixed with 1 ml of Bradford solution. After 10 min extinction was measured at 595 nm in duplicates. Protein content mg/ml was calculated with the standard curve $y = m * x + b$ as:

$$\text{Absorption: } y = m * x + b$$

$$x = \frac{\Sigma y - b}{m} \quad [\mu\text{g/pipett.vol.}]$$

$$x = \frac{x}{\text{pipetted volume } (\mu\text{l})} \quad [\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}]$$

$$\text{Protein content: } Pc = x * 5 \text{ (dilution factor) } [\text{mg/ml}]$$

4.5 Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using SigmaStat (Version 3.5, Systat Software, San Jose, California, U.S.) and plotted using SigmaPlot (Version 14., Systat Software, San Jose, California, U.S.). Data were expressed as means with a standard error of the means (SEM). Differences between groups were examined using analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the Normality Test and the Equal Variance Test, followed with the Student-Newman-Keuls comparisons for factor: molt stage, acclimation temperature or combination of those two factors: molt stage within certain temperature or acclimation temp within certain molt stage. The degrees of correlation were analysed by linear regression with the Normality Test and the Constant Variance Test and determined Pearson correlation coefficients (r) and the goodness of fit (R^2). At $p \leq 0.05$, differences were considered statistically significant.

Outliers were identified according to Nalimov (Nalimov *et al.* 1963) and eliminated before further statistical analyses.

5 Results

5.1 Determination of maximal ion transporting ATPases capacities

5.1.1 Optimisation of ATPases activity tests for *M. magister*

For measuring the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase, Ca²⁺-ATPase and Mg²⁺-ATPase activity in the hepatopancreas of the crab *M. magister* assays needed to be optimized first by testing several assay buffers: NaK ATPase assay buffer, Ca + ATPase assay buffers mainly differing by the amount of cations and the buffer components. These measurements were combined with different inhibitors - ouabain, vanadate, thapsigargin to find the maximal inhibition and inhibitor specific activity. The optimisation was done at 20°C assay temperature.

The Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity was successfully determined with the commonly used NaK ATPase assay buffer (Deigweiher et al. 2008) combined with Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase specific inhibitor – ouabain (Pchejetski et al., 2003) and in this combination, it was measured in the further analyses (see 5.1.2). In Ca²⁺ based buffers, the inhibition by ouabain was reduced by one order of magnitude (data not shown).

To determine Ca²⁺-ATPase activity several Ca ATPase assay buffers (Saborido et al., 1999) (with different Ca concentrations: 0 μM, 50 μM, 100 μM, 250 μM, 500 μM, 5 mM) were tested with both the SERCA specific inhibitor –thapsigargin (Lyttong et al., 1991)(**Figure 3A**) and the wide range P-type ATPase inhibitor vanadate (Csermely et al., 1985a) for the detection of the plasma membrane Ca²⁺-ATPase (PMCA) (**Figure 3B**). No significant differences in the activities with increasing Ca²⁺ concentration were seen in the activity detected by thapsigargin and variations between different tissue preparation prevented clear evidence for a Ca²⁺ dependent ATPase activity of the SERCA type. The activity detected by vanadate showed a general slightly decreasing pattern with increasing Ca²⁺ concentration, even though the standard errors were large (**Figure 3B**). However, the differences were not statistically significant (P = 0,304). This confirms the previously described pattern that high Ca²⁺ concentrations inhibit Ca²⁺-dependent ATPase activity (Simonides and van Hardeveld, 1990). A similar pattern was observed in the total activity (**Figure 3C**), but the differences were neither statistically significant (P = 0,237).

As a conclusion, no clear evidence for Ca²⁺-ATPase (either SERCA or PMCA) could be drawn from these tests and we decided to measure general ATPase activity using the wide range P-type ATPase inhibitor vanadate in the Ca (-) ATPase assay buffer. As the ouabain inhibition in this buffer -containing 100mM KCl, 5 mM MgCl₂ and 0.2 mM

EGTA, but no NaCl as relevant ions-was only weak, we assigned this activity as Mg²⁺-ATPase.

A) Activity detected by thapsigargin

B) Activity detected by vanadate

Figure 3 Ca²⁺ dependency of ATPase activities in hepatopancreas. **A)** Activity detected by thapsigargin (SERCA specific inhibitor); **B)** Activity detected by vanadate -wide range P-type ATPase inhibitor; **C)** Total activity without inhibitor present. Values are given as means ± SEM (n = 2-5).

5.1.2 Molt stage and temperature dependent Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase capacities

The Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase capacities in the hepatopancreas of the crab *M. magister* acclimated to 10, 15 and 20 °C for 14 days and assigned molt stage (Wittmann et al., 2018) is presented in **Figure 4**. For all crab acclimation temperatures (10°C: **4A**), 15°C: **4B**) and 20°C: **4C**) the activity increased significantly with increasing assay temperature (P<0,001 for all temperatures acclimation). Activities in stage C, D0 and D1 overlap in the 10°C and 15°C acclimated animals at relatively low values (**Figure 4A** and **4B** respectively), while activities in the stage D2 and D3 reached high values and differed significantly from the other molt stages (10°C acclimated crabs - D3 vs. C:p<0.001; D2 vs. C:p<0.001; 15° acclimated crabs -D2 vs. C:p= 0.030; D3 vs. C:p=0.505). Between D2 and D3 the difference is not statistically significant (10°C acclimated crabs - D3 vs. D2 P= 0,207; 15° acclimated crabs - D2 vs. D3 P = 0,654) likely due to the low n numbers in these groups.

The pattern of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity in the 20°C acclimated animals differed slightly from the other acclimation temperatures (**Figure 4C**). The activities in stage C and D0 were very similar to each other, reaching the lowest values among the stages and compared to the respective groups at lower acclimations temperatures. Activities in the stages D1 and D2 were also similar, reaching values slightly higher than the first pair (C and D0; D1 vs. C: P = 0,019; D2 vs. D0: P = 0,006). The stage D3 differed from all other molt stages reaching the highest values however, this difference was not always statistically significant

-D3 vs. C: $p < 0,001$; D3 vs. D0 $P < 0,001$; D3 vs. D1: $P = 0,075$; D3 vs. D2 $P = 0,065$), due to low n numbers and reasonable individual variation. In general, activity reached the highest values in the 10°C acclimated crabs with a maximum of about 300 $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{h} \cdot \text{g}(\text{FW}))$, while 15°C and 20°C acclimated crabs remained at a maximum of about 200 $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{h} \cdot \text{g}(\text{FW}))$.

Even though it seems that there are differences in the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity between acclimation temperatures, the statistical significance was reported only for stages C and D0 between animals acclimated to 10°C and 15°C – stage C $P < 0,001$, D0 $P = 0,022$ and acclimated to 15°C and 20°C – stage C $P = 0,007$, D0 $P = 0,002$. Presented statistics were done for the 15°C assay temperature data, as it represented the control temperature, In transformation was necessary in order to meet statistical requirements mostly. Together, two-way ANOVA provided evidence that molt stage has a significant effect on Na^+/K^+ -ATPase capacities, which is additionally affected by temperature (D3 vs. D0 10°C acclimated crabs $P < 0,001$; 15°C acclimated $P = 0,268$; 20°C acclimated $P < 0,001$). The interaction of these two factors, individual variations and the low n numbers for some molt stages prevented more detailed conclusions.

Figure 4 Temperature-dependent maximal Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity with respect to molt stages in hepatopancreas crude extract samples obtained from *M. magister* acclimated to 10°C –**A**), 15°C –**B**) and 20°C –**C**). C –intermolt, D0 –early premolt, D1 –mid premolt, D2, D3 –late premolt. The double-sided arrow indicate the increase in the enzyme activity between stages. Values are given as means \pm SEM (n= 3-9 per treatment in stage C, D0, D1, D2; n=1-2 per treatment in stage D3).

5.1.3 Molt stage and temperature dependent Mg^{2+} -ATPase capacities

Maximum Mg^{2+} -ATPase activities in the hepatopancreas of *M. magister* were very low (around 40 $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{h}\cdot\text{g}(\text{FW}))$); **Figure 5**) in comparison to the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity. The activity increases with the increasing assay temperature (except stage D2 in the 10°C acclimation) for all acclimation temperatures (10°C: **5A**), 15°C: **5B** and 20°C: **5C**), however

there is no other clear pattern in the activity of this ion dependent ATPase and no proper statistic could be done here (normality test: failed, $P < 0,050$; equal variance test: failed, $P < 0,050$ - concerning 15°C assay temperature and \ln transformation). However, some preliminary trends may be present. Overall, the response of the different molt stages varied with acclimation temperature indicating an interaction of both factors. Moreover, the thermal sensitivity of some molt stages differ largely between acclimation temperatures, e.g. for D3 and for D2.

A) 10°C acclimated crabs

B) 15°C acclimated crabs

Figure 5 Temperature-dependent maximal Mg^{2+} -ATPase activity with respect to molt stages in hepatopancreas crude extract sampled from *M. magister* acclimated to 10°C –**A**), 15°C –**B**) and 20°C –**C**). C –intermolt, D0 –early premolt, D1 –mid premolt, D2, D3 –late premolt. Values are given as means \pm SEM (n= 3-8 per treatment in stage C, D0, D1, D2; n= 1-2 per treatment in stage D3).

5.2 Protein expression of ion transporting ATPases

5.2.1 Validation of antibodies for Western analyses

Since no primary antibodies targeted against any ATPase of *M. magister* exists, heterologous antibodies were used in the present study. Therefore, the specificity of primary antibodies on the target species *M. magister* was tested for the following five antibodies: Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α , Anti-Hsp70, F_1F_0 -ATP synthase α , CaF2 serum, Anti Ca pump PMCA [5F10]. At the beginning of the validation process, all tested antibodies were able to detect some promising protein bands in the heart and the gills of the target crab species *M. magister*, however no signal was detected in the hepatopancreas: The Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α antibody ($\alpha 5$) detected a protein in the control fish gills (C: *Notothenia coriiceps*), in the crab *M. magister* heart tissue (H) and the gill tissue (G) at around 100 kDa, which was absent in the hepatopancreas tissue (HP) (**Figure 6A**). The Anti-Hsp70 antibody (HSP 70 - region involved in ATP binding) detected a protein signal at around 70 kDa in the control fish tissue (C) and a weak signal in both *M. magister* tissues - the heart (H) and the gill (G)(**Figure 6B**). The double band for the gill may represent several isoforms of the Hsp70, as known for many species. Again, no signal was detected in the hepatopancreas (HP) (**Figure 6B**). The mitochondrial F_1F_0 -ATP synthase α antibody detected very strong protein signals

at the expected size in the control fish tissue (C), *M. magister* gills (G) and heart (H), however in all tissues a lot of degradation products were detected as well mostly due to the high sensitivity of this antibody (**Figure 6C**). Despite this high sensitivity, no signal was obtained for hepatopancreas (HP) (**Figure 6C**). The CaF2 serum (SERCA1) detected a signal in the control fish tissue (C) and in the crab *M. magister* heart (H), however not within the range of the antigen molecular weight (110 kDa; **Figure 6D**). No signal was detected in the crab gills (G) and the hepatopancreas (HP) (**Figure 6D**). The Anti Ca pump PMCA [5F10] antibody detected a signal in all tested tissues and recognized a protein of about 140 kDa in the crab heart (H) and gills (G) representing PMCA ATPase (**Figure 6E**). However, the signals detected in the hepatopancreas (HP) may only represent degradation products.

E) Anti Ca pump PMCA [5F10]

Figure 6 Western Blot analysis of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase $\alpha[\alpha 5]$ -**A**), Anti-Hsp70 -**B**), F_1F_0 -ATP synthase α -**C**), CaF2 serum -**D**), Anti Ca pump PMCA [5F10] -**E**) in the crab *M. magister* hepatopancreas (HP), heart (H), gills (G) and in the control (C) fish gills (*Notothenia coriiceps*); crude extract (CE), cytosolic fraction (CF) and membrane fraction (MF).

As these first results indicate some degradation and the hepatopancreas is known for its high protease content, additional inhibitors (vanadate, PMSF) were added to the extraction buffer and the western blotting was repeated for some antibodies. Furthermore, the crude extracts were processed into cytosolic and membrane fractions (as already presented for the Anti Ca pump PMCA [5F10] –Figure 10E), to validate the membrane localization of the detected proteins and to increase the detection limit of the antibodies due to the enrichment of the target proteins in the membrane fraction. Doing so, a strong signal for the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase could be detected at the proper size in the membrane fraction of *M. magister* hepatopancreas (**Figure 7A**). The same pattern could be obtained for heart and gills (**Figure 8**) but without degradation products, which are still present to some extent in HP samples (**Figure 7A**; **Figure 8**). Thus, the α antibody Na^+/K^+ -ATPase [$\alpha 5$] seem to be specific for the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase in *M. magister*, and usable for quantification in hepatopancreas. Other tested antibodies for the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase were not suitable: with H300 only degradation products were detected and Na^+/K^+ -ATPase $\alpha 6$ did not detect any signal (data not shown).

The Anti Ca pump PMCA antibody [5F10] detected signals in the membrane fraction (MF) of the hepatopancreas however, degradation products predominated (**Figure 7B**). Repeated experiments with the use of the PMCA antibody [5F10] with gill and heart did not allow to obtain better results, there those presented in the **Figure 6E** (data not shown). Both

antibodies detected only degradation products in the crude extract (CE) and the cytosolic fraction (CF) of *M. magister* hepatopancreas. Thus, for the final quantification of protein expression the extracts used for the enzyme measurements could not be used. Instead, membrane fractions of remaining tissue subsamples were prepared using the additional set of protease inhibitors. Furthermore, to improve the recovery of the membrane proteins after ultracentrifugation, 4µl extraction buffer per mg tissue was used instead of 2 µl.

Figure 7 Western Blot analysis of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α [$\alpha 5$] -**A**) and the Anti Ca pump PMCA [5F10] -**B**) in the crab *M. magister* hepatopancreas (HP) crude extract (CE), cytosolic fraction (CF) and membrane fraction (MF).

Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α [$\alpha 5$]

Figure 8 Western Blot analysis of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α [$\alpha 5$] in hepatopancreas crude extract –CE, cytosolic fraction –CF and membrane fraction -MF of *M. magister*.

5.2.2 Quantification of ATPase expression

Due to the limited amount of remaining tissue subsamples changes in the relative protein expression of ATPases in *M. magister* hepatopancreas could only be analysed in some groups by use of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α antibody [α 5] and Anti Ca pump PMCA antibody [5F10]. Stage D3 were not quantified due to the lack of material. Each of the acclimation temperature experiment included hepatopancreas samples of all four molt stages in triplicate (10°C acclimated crabs) or quadruplicate (15°, 20°C acclimated crabs). Additionally, the extraction buffer of the animals acclimated to 10°C included inhibitor vanadate and PMSF, while extraction buffer of the animals acclimated to 15°, 20°C included vanadate, PMSF and soy bean trypsin inhibitor additional to the already present general protease inhibitor mix.

As visualized exemplary for the 15°C acclimated specimens molt stage altered significantly the expression of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase in the hepatopancreas of *M. magister*. Moreover, the signals in the membrane fractions were very distinct, and no degradation products were obvious (**Figure 9**).

Figure 9 Detection of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α subunit in hepatopancreas membrane fractions of *M. magister* acclimated to 15°C with respect to different molt stages. C –intermolt, D0 –early premolt,

D1 –mid premolt, D2 –late premolt. Samples of each molt stages run in quadruplicate with the extraction buffer included vanadate, PMSF and soy bean trypsin inhibitor.

As illustrated in **Figure 10A**, protein expression of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase in 10°C acclimated crabs was significantly increased in stage D0 compared to stage C and D2, reaching approximately 4 fold higher expression (4,219 ± 0,222 at stage D0; 1,000 ± 0,0507 at stage C, P < 0,001; 0,756 ± 0,287 at stage D2; P =<0,001). The difference between stages C and D2 was not significant P = 0,382. Unfortunately, no signals were not obtained for stage D1 despite using the same extraction procedure. At higher acclimation temperatures, protein levels of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase were also increased in response to proceeding molt cycle. In 15°C acclimated crabs, the protein expression increased gradually with progressing molt cycle, reaching nearly 4 fold higher expression in the stage D2 (3,769 ± 0,248 at stage D2; 1,000 ± 0,231 at stage C, P <0,001) (**Figure 9**; **Figure 10B**). In 20°C acclimated crabs, the protein expression changed much less than at lower acclimation temperature reaching only 2-fold expression in D2 (1,990 ± 0,648 at stage D2; 1,000 ± 0,354 at stage C), but this increase was not statistically significant (P = 0,327) (**Figure 10C**).

Samples of the 15°C and 20°C acclimated crabs were also tested with Anti Ca²⁺ pump PMCA antibody [5F10] however, the signal was full of degradation products besides the presence of the most complex inhibitor combination, and a proper band was not detectable (data not shown). The same extracts from 15°C and 20°C acclimated crabs were further tested with the F₁F₀-ATP synthase α antibody showing positive clear signal bands and no degradation (data not shown) similar to the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase (**Figure 9**), indicating an overall improvement of the extraction protocol due to the use of soy bean trypsin inhibitor. Thus, the PMCA seemed to be more sensitive to degradation than the other membrane ATPases.

A) 10°C acclimated crabs

B) 15°C acclimated crabs

Figure 10 Western Blot analysis of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α subunit with respect to molt stages in hepatopancreas crude extract samples obtained from *M. magister* acclimated to 10°C –**A**), 15°C –**B**) and 20°C –**C**). C –intermolt, D0 –early premolt, D1 –mid premolt, D2 –late premolt. Values are given as means \pm SEM (n = 2-4 per stage). Different letters denote significant differences between molt stages (a/b). Extraction buffer of the animals acclimated to 10°C included vanadate and PMSF and extraction buffer of the animals acclimated to 15° and 20°C included vanadate, PMSF and soy bean trypsin inhibitor.

5.3 Total protein content in hepatopancreas

Changes in the total protein content of the *M. magister* hepatopancreas between animals acclimated to 10°C, 15°C, 20°C with respect to molt stages were quantified accordingly to Bradford (1976). Overall, protein content in the crude extract was between 3.5 and 4.5 mg/ml extraction buffer and quite comparable between different acclimation temperatures and molt stages (**Figure 11A**). In the 10°C acclimated animals a weak statistical difference between stages C and D2 ($p = 0,05$) could be observed. Similar, a small significant difference could be detected for the animals acclimated to 20°C (**Figure 11A**: between stages C and D1, with $p = 0,047$). At 15°C acclimation temperature, molt stage had no significant effect on total protein content.

In the hepatopancreas membrane fraction, only small variations in protein content may exist between 10°C acclimation temperature and the warmer temperatures (**Figure 11B**) but due to the very little sample number this was not significant. Molt stage seemed to have no effect on membrane protein content. The fluctuations in between stages were not statistically significant.

Figure 11 Bradford analysis of the protein content in the hepatopancreas crude extract –A) and membrane fraction –B) of the crab *M.magister* acclimated to 10°C, 15°C and 20°C, with respect to molt stages. C –intermolt, D0 –early premolt, D1 –mid premolt, D2 –late premolt, D3 – late premolt; Values are given as means \pm SEM (n = 2-10 per treatment; except D3 15°C –reflects only 1 value). Different letters denote significant differences between molt stages (a/b).

5.4 Correlation analysis between Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity and its relative expression

The degrees of correlation between Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity and expression were analysed by plotting the ln (Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase activity) (measured at a common assay temperature) against the respective Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase relative expression (determined in all analysed specimens) of the same hepatopancreas sample (**Figure 12**). The 15°C assay temperature activities were taken as this temperature represents the control for *M. magister* in this experiment (Wittmann et al, 2018). A weak, positive correlation between ln (Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase activity) and protein expression level seemed exist, however this was not statistically significant (P= 0,295; R² = 0,0405).

Figure 12 Correlation between ln (Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase activity) (measured at a common assay temperature of 15°C) and Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase relative expression (determined in all three acclimation temperature: 10°C, 15°C, 20°C) of the crab *M. magister* observed in the same hepatopancreas samples. P =0,295; R² =0,0405; N = 29.

5.5 Correlation analysis between mRNA level of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase and its activity

For a deeper understanding of the regulation patterns the mRNA expression level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α -subunit determined as described in Wittmann et al. 2018 were used (mRNA data provided by dr Wittmann – unpublished).

The degrees of correlation between mRNA level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase and Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase activity in the hepatopancreas of the crab *M. magister* were analysed by plotting the mRNA

level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α-subunit against ln (Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase activity) (measured at a common assay temperature of 15°C) from the same tissue samples (**Figure 13**). Ln transformation of the activity was done to meet statistical requirements. There is a positive relationship between the mRNA level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α-subunit and Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase, even though data are varying largely (P <0,001). There is a clear progression with molt stage and both mRNA level and activity rise.

Figure 13 Correlations between mRNA level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α-subunit and Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase ln activity (measured in the 15°C assay temperature) of the crab *M. magister* observed in the same hepatopancreas samples. P <0,001; R² =0,239 ; N = 55.

5.6 Correlation analysis between mRNA level of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase and its protein expression

The degrees of correlation between mRNA level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase and Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase protein expression in the hepatopancreas of the crab *M. magister* were analysed by plotting the mRNA level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α-subunit (data provided by dr Wittmann – unpublished) against Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase expression (determined in all three acclimation temperature: 10°C, 15°C, 20°C) from the same tissue samples (**Figure 14**). There is a significant positive relationship between the mRNA level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α-subunit and Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase relative expression, even though data are varying largely (P =0,013).

Figure 14 Correlations between mRNA level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α-subunit and Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase relative expression (determined in all three acclimation temperature: 10°C, 15°C, 20°C) of the crab *M. magister* observed in the same hepatopancreas samples. $P = 0,013$; $R^2 = 0,206$; $N = 29$.

6 Discussion

Within the scope of this thesis, the combined effect of temperature and molt stages on ion regulation was analysed in the hepatopancreas of the crab *M. magister*. By the establishment of assays, the specific ion-transporting ATPase capacities test systems were determined. Another experiment aimed to find some specific antibodies for the determination of the ATPases protein expression. Further analyses focused on the determination of the effect of temperature and molt cycle on the ATPase capacities and the protein expression. Furthermore, some implications for transepithelial ion transport were made by determining the total protein level within the main ion transporting structure –membrane fraction and compared with the crude extract. Also, possible relationships between determined actions and in addition, between mRNA ATPase level (obtained from Dr. Wittmann) were analysed.

6.1 Establishment of assays for specific determination of ion-transporting ATPase capacities

Optimisation of ATPases activity has resulted in the successful determination of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity and a Mg^{2+} dependent, vanadate sensitive ATPase. For Na^+/K^+ -ATPase well established assay for measuring the ATPase function in gills of fish and crustaceans (Deigweiher et al., 2008; Henry et al., 2002) using a high Na^+ /low K^+ buffer system could be easily adapted to the hepatopancreas of *M. magister*. The fractional inhibition by ouabain was in the range of 20-60%. As the determination of the specific ATPase function relies on the subtraction of two measurements, thereby increasing the overall error of the final result, the high fractional inhibition by ouabain resulted overall in reliable and reproducible measurements. Moreover, the fractional inhibition in the presence of vanadate, the general inhibitor of all P-type ATPases, was always about 10 % higher than with ouabain indicating the activity of further P-type ATPases in this buffer system besides the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase. Instead, in all Ca^{2+} related buffer systems, the inhibition by ouabain was very weak and hardly reproducible, whereas vanadate inhibited a reasonable fraction of the total ATPase activity. Moreover, total activities determined in the Ca^{2+} buffer systems were always smaller than in the high Na^+ /low K^+ buffer system. Thus it seems plausible that the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase did not contribute significantly to the vanadate sensitive ATPase function in the Ca^{2+} buffer systems. Thus, at this state, the optimisation data indicated a reliable and reproducible test system for the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase.

The activity detected by vanadate showed a small but in general slightly decreasing pattern with increasing Ca^{2+} concentration, even though the standard errors were large. Thus,

this confirms the previously described pattern that high Ca^{2+} concentrations inhibit Ca^{2+} -dependent ATPase activity (Simonides and van Hardeveld, 1990). This is caused by the so-called back-inhibition phenomenon in which Ca^{2+} -ATPase activity ceases when intravesicular Ca^{2+} rises to millimolar levels which leads to saturation of low-affinity, inhibitory Ca^{2+} -binding sites on the enzyme. In order to continued maximal Ca^{2+} -ATPase activity, the permeation of the vesicles is needed with either a Ca^{2+} ionophore, e.g. A23187, or with detergent, so as to prevent the buildup of intravesicular Ca^{2+} (Simonides and van Hardeveld, 1990). At the beginning of the optimisation of ATPases activity we had only used desoxycholic acid as detergent, but during optimisation, we added additionally the Ca^{2+} ionophore A23187, as described for some published protocols (Saborido et al., 1999; Simonides and van Hardeveld, 1990), thus no inhibition of the Ca^{2+} -ATPase function by the build up of an electrochemical gradient should have occurred.

Also, no significant differences in the activities with increasing Ca^{2+} concentration were seen in the activity detected by thapsigargin (SERCA specific inhibitor). The fraction of inhibited ATPase function was very low in comparison to the total activity, and additionally feigned negative activities with high error bars (similarly to the vanadate sensitive activity) were detected. However here no decreasing pattern was reported. This, prevented us to detect any strong Ca^{2+} dependency. According to Lichtman et al., (1981) the maximum activation of the Ca^{2+} -ATPase, is reached at a free Ca^{2+} concentration of ca. 4-5 μM , and such amount of free ion is present at about 125 μM CaCl_2 buffer. At both vanadate and thapsigargin detected activity were indeed slightly higher at around 100 μM concentration. As for the thapsigargin no decreasing pattern was reported (in a contract to vanadate) the peak at this certain point following by a slight decrease, might reflect this maximum Ca^{2+} free saturation. That might suggest that the reported thapsigargin sensitive ATPase activity was driven by Ca^{2+} free, but the vanadate ATPase was not. Furthermore, the activity measurements could be influenced by the degradation processes as enzymes degrade over time. The final expression analyses revealed that even after adding several additional protease inhibitors to the extraction buffer, the PMCA was much more susceptible to degradation than the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase. Thus, it would confirm the important role of the degradation process influenced the Ca^{2+} -ATPase activity assessment, as only the normal protease inhibitor set was present.

As no clear evidence for Ca^{2+} -ATPase (either SERCA or PMCA) could be drawn, and measurements in the wide range P-type ATPase inhibitor vanadate in the Ca (-) ATPase assay buffer (no CaCl_2 added to the buffer), revealed reasonable activity, we have decided to use this set to prove some activity. As the ouabain inhibition in this buffer -containing 100mM KCl, 5 mM MgCl_2 and 0.2 mM EGTA, but no NaCl as relevant ions- was only weak, we assigned this as Mg^{2+} dependent ATPase activity.

To conclude, there was some Ca^{2+} -ATPase function in hepatopancreas as we may see a weak Ca^{2+} dependency. Due to the fact that the specific SERCA inhibitor –thapsigargin did not work, but vanadate did, what was indicated by the decrease at high Ca^{2+} concentration, it would be possible that the PMCA is a part of this inhibition. Since the activity was already high in the Ca (-) buffer (no CaCl_2 added to the buffer), we could not demonstrate a clear Ca^{2+} dependency. This might be due to the presence of other P-type ATPases like Mg^{2+} ATPases, or due to very high Ca^{2+} affinity of the existing Ca^{2+} -ATPases. This second explanation could not be ruled out since no ultrapure Ca^{2+} free buffer system was used. The presence of EGTA should have captured all free Ca^{2+} derived from other contaminated salt and buffer components, however Ca^{2+} free may differ even when EGTA is at its best in terms of buffer capacity (Bers et al., 1994). Therefore, the reasonable detected activity in the high possibility of no Ca^{2+} presence, was named as “ Mg^{2+} -dependent, vanadate sensitive ATPase” further called in the thesis as Mg^{2+} -ATPase activity/capacity.

It is also worth to mention that some reasonable thapsigargin inhibition was detected when using the NaK ATPase assay buffer. Although this buffer did not contain any specific Ca^{2+} salts, impurities of Ca^{2+} from other salts and buffer components may be sufficient to promote a specific SERCA activity, as EGTA was absent in this buffer and SERCA usually possesses a high apparent affinity to Ca^{2+} ($K_{0.5}$ 0.17 ± 0.02 ; Vandecaetsbeek et al., 2009). Clearly, tests with other buffers like the NaK ATPase assay buffer in the presence/absence of EGTA and Ca^{2+} seems to be promising in developing a specific SERCA assay for the hepatopancreas of *M. magister*.

6.2 Effect of temperature on ATPases capacities

Analysis of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity in the hepatopancreas tissue of the crab *M. magister* revealed a clear increase with increasing assay temperature for all crabs at all acclimation temperatures (10°C – **Figure 4A**, 15°C –**4B**) and 20°C –**4C**). This is in line with the Q10 effect, which says that increasing temperatures elevate the rate of biological activity (Hochachka and Somero, 2002). Activities in the stage D2 and D3 differed significantly from the other stages reaching the highest values and thereby confirming the increase in ATPases activity just prior to molting, when massive ion fluxes occur (Towle and Mangum, 1985). This pattern was clearly visible for 10°C and 15°C acclimated crabs (**Figure 4A, 4B**), while 20°C acclimated crabs showed a slightly different pattern (**Figure 4C**). Only the stage D3 differed from other stages, however this difference was not always statistically significant. Increased Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity support the calcification process and allows for fast Ca^{2+} transport through the cell membrane and further deposition in the exoskeleton (Wheatly et al., 2002 a, b). Considering the differences in the acclimation temperature, the difference of stage D2 and D3 -when compared with the rest of stages -was the strongest in 10°C

acclimated animals and vanished with the increasing acclimation temperature (**Figure 4**: visualized by the double-sided arrow, where less increase in the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity within stages is visible, by less distance between datapoints).

This indicates a reduced sensitivity for changing the temperature on the ATPases activity by the warmer acclimated animals (15°C, 20°C) and a significant interaction of both factors, temperature and molt stage, on the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase function. Moreover, the most efficient ion transport/ATPases capacities were found in the D2/D3 stages of 10°C acclimated crabs, which represents thermal compensation to maintain ion homeostasis in the cold (Hochachka and Somero, 2002). The data thus support the concept of metabolic cold compensation in that the same effect is visible for animals acclimated just to different temperatures, as for evolutionary cold adapted polar species compared to lower latitude species (Hochachka and Somero 2002; Young et al., 2006).

Together, two-way ANOVA provided evidence that molt stage has a significant effect on Na^+/K^+ -ATPase capacities, which is additionally affected by temperature (D3 vs. D0 10°C acclimated crabs $P < 0,001$; 15°C acclimated $P = 0,268$; 20°C acclimated $P < 0,001$). The interaction of two factors - individual variations and the low n numbers for some molt stages prevented more detailed conclusions.

In contrast, the Mg^{2+} dependent ATPase activity only increased with increasing assay temperature, as expected from a common Q10 effect however, no other pattern in terms of molt stages or acclimation temperature was visible (**Figure 5A, 5B, 5C**). This was mainly due to the failure of statistical assumptions (Normality Test: Failed, $P < 0,050$; Equal Variance Test: Failed, $P < 0,050$ - concerns 15°C assay temperature In activity). The high variance in the data indicate some difficulties in determining the true activities because of the high requirements in terms of the molecular mechanism of working. The MgATP is the substrate for the Mg^{2+} -ATPase, which must be present at a low concentration, otherwise, the substrate inhibits the enzyme (Nozadze et al., 2015). Additionally, the free Mg^{2+} and free ATP ions modify the enzyme. Together with the technical issues discussed above (measuring total activity versus inhibitor insensitive activity) this interferes with a proper Mg^{2+} -ATPase activity measurement. For final conclusions about the effect of acclimation temperature and molt stage on Mg^{2+} -ATPase function the measurements should be repeated with the use of MgATP avoiding excess free Mg^{2+} and ATP ions.

However, some preliminary trends may be concluded. In general, Mg^{2+} dependent ATPase activity level was very low in comparison to the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity. This is in line with the concept that the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase is the central Na^+ pump establishing the electrochemical gradients for all other transport processes across the membranes, whereas the Mg^{2+} dependent ATPase has only specialized functions. Besides Mg^{2+} is actively

done-regulated in the hemolymph compared to the seawater, whereas the Na^+ concentration is almost equal between hemolymph and seawater (Towle and Mangum, 1985). Thus, reasonable Mg^{2+} transport must be considered, however it remains obscure, whether the hepatopancreas is involved in this process. The response of the different molt stages varied with acclimation temperature indicating an interaction of these two factors. High activities were repeatedly observed for the stages D1, D2 and D3 (**Figure 5**) indicating a role for the Mg^{2+} dependent ATPase in the molting process. Certainly, the test system and extraction protocol need further optimisation to substantiate and extend these preliminary conclusions.

6.3 Determination of protein expression of ATPases with specific antibodies

The optimisation of ATPases quantification has revealed that in general hepatopancreas tissue of the crab *M. magister* seems to be challenging for protein quantification in comparison to other tissues like gills or heart from the same species. At the beginning of the validation process, all tested antibodies (Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α , Anti-Hsp70, F_1F_0 -ATP synthase α , CaF2 serum, Anti Ca pump PMCA [5F10]) were able to detect some promising protein bands in the heart (H) and the gills (G) of the target crab species *M. magister*, however no signal was detected in the hepatopancreas (HP) (**Figure 6**). Detection in the hepatopancreas tissue was somehow interfered (**Figure 6A, 6B, 6C, 6D**), and if detected a lot of degradation products became visible (**Figure 6E**). As these first results indicate some degradation and the hepatopancreas is known for its high protease content, additional inhibitors (vanadate, PMSF, soy bean trypsin inhibitor) were added to the extraction buffer. Furthermore, the crude extracts were processed into cytosolic and membrane fractions, to validate the membrane localization of the detected proteins and to increase the detection limit of the antibodies due to the enrichment of the target proteins in the membrane fraction.

All of this allowed us to detect a strong, specific signal of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase in the hepatopancreas (**Figure 7A**) however, the signals obtained for heart and gills (**Figure 8**) without any degradation products confirmed the hepatopancreas as being a problematic tissue. This clearly demonstrates how important it is to determine the right set of inhibitors for every tissue in order to avoid any degradation of the target protein, which may interfere with proper quantification. Besides its tougher texture, the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase could be extracted and detected much easier and reproducible from gill and heart tissue. Based on the well determined gill and the heart signal of the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α and even the hepatopancreas signal (**Figure 8**) we can conclude that the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase protein is present in the crude

extract (CE) and membrane fraction (MF). In the cytosolic fractions (CF) Na^+/K^+ -ATPase was only detected in the heart tissue, however only in very low amounts, indicating some impurities during the enrichment process.

Modification of the method was not that successful for the detection of the PMCA. The use of the Anti Ca pump PMCA antibody [5F10] has resulted in the detected signals in the membrane fraction (MF) of the hepatopancreas however, degradation products predominated (**Figure 7B**). Repeated experiments with the use of the PMCA antibody [5F10] with gill and heart did not allow to obtain better results, there those presented in the **Figure 6E** (data not shown).

Additionally, the protein level differs within the tissues. This might results from their different physiological needs. Gills for example, not only has a respiratory function but is also important for ion homeostasis (Henry et al., 2012), which makes them a competitor for the hepatopancreas with respect to molting. In postmolt, the gills cause massive net Ca^{2+} influx (Gao and Wheatly, 2004). However, the study by Wheatly et al., 2002, has reported that lobster hepatopancreas has 46-fold larger Ca^{2+} uptake capacities than the gill. In the heart of the crab, the Na^+ , K^+ and Ca^{2+} concentrations have an important effect on contraction (reviewed from Lindeman, 1928), which necessitates a tight regulation of these ions by ion-transporting ATPases. The results from this studies indicate that, the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase α was more abundant in the heart tissue than in the gills (**Figure 8**) and Plasma Membrane Ca^{2+} -ATPase (PMCA) seems to be equally expressed in the gills and in the heart (**Figure 6E**).

The only usable antibody for the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase quantification in the hepatopancreas of this studies target species *M. magister* was Na^+/K^+ -ATPase [$\alpha 5$] (despite testing of the other antibodies H300 and Na^+/K^+ -ATPase $\alpha 6$). As the Anti PMCA antibody [5F10] detected only degradation products in the crude extract (CE) and the cytosolic fraction (CF) of *M. magister* hepatopancreas, the final quantification of protein expression was performed in the membrane fractions for all ATPases.

All of the used improvements allowed us to detect clear Na^+/K^+ -ATPase bands and therefore determine Na^+/K^+ -ATPase relative expression (**Figure 9, 10**). The Anti Ca pump PMCA [5F10] antibody was also tested however, the signal revealed degradation products besides the presence of the most complex inhibitor combination. In the final experiment, the proper band was not detectable (images not shown) what prevented a proper quantification of this protein. The extracts from 15°C and 20°C acclimated crabs were also tested with the F_1F_0 -ATP synthase α antibody showing positive clear signal bands and no degradation (data not shown) similar to the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase (**Figure 9**), indicating an overall improvement of the extraction protocol due to the use of soy bean trypsin inhibitor.

Thus, the PMCA seemed to be more sensitive to degradation than the other membrane ATPases. Together, a proper detection system for the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase (and the F₁F₀-ATP synthase α) could be established for *M. magister* during this Master thesis. The data indicate that the Anti Ca pump PMCA [5F10] antibody is also specific for the PMCA from *M. magister*, however, further improvement of the extraction protocol is needed.

6.4 Effect of temperature on the protein expression of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase

Relative Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase expression was significantly increased in 10°C acclimated crabs for stage D0 compared to the stages C and D2, reaching approximately 4fold higher expression (**Figure 10A**). The difference between stages C and D2 was not significant. Despite using the same extraction procedure the stage D1 was not detected. Therefore, in proper treatment of the tissue during sampling may have caused this complete absence of any signal. For 15°C and 20°C acclimated crabs the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase protein level also increased with further molt stage (**Figure 10B, 10C**) but while in 15°C the increase was also nearly 4fold (**Figure 9; Figure 10B**), the increase was only ca. 2fold for the 20°C and not statistically significant (**Figure 10C**). Thus, warm acclimation caused a reduction in the accumulation of the enzyme concentration with proceeding molt stages. Less protein at warmer temperature may thus indicate also thermal compensation, as this reduced amount of proteins may still be able to perform properly due to the Q10 effect. Nevertheless, the activity data indicate lower thermal responsiveness in 20°C acclimated animals compared to the lower temperature groups (**Figure 4**). Thus, warm acclimated crabs may not react as sensitive to acute temperature fluctuations than the cold-acclimated ones. As temperature fluctuations more frequently occur during summer times at least close to the shore lines in the tidal zones, this reduced responsiveness might be an adaptation to this environment, as it prevents an overshoot of ATPase function (and ATP expenditure). However, less responsiveness may handicap an elevated ion transport needed prior to molting event in warm waters. Less efficient ion transport in warmer temperatures might cause less efficient building of a new carapace and therefore potential danger for the animal, as after ecdysis the body is very soft and the animal has no external protection. Since feeding pressure might be higher during summer due to the more-active life style of marine life including the predators, there is great pressure to harden the new carapace as fast as possible by the use of effective ion transport (Neufeld and Cameron, 1992). As a global picture, Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase concentration as well as Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase capacities increased in response to proceeding molt cycle, which helps in the calcification process allowing for an elevated Ca²⁺ transport and further deposition in the exoskeleton according to the existing models (**Figure 1; Table 1**). It also supports the establishing local osmotic

gradients to induce water influx across the epithelia, which inflates the new exoskeleton. Warm acclimation, however caused a modification of this mechanism. The warmer acclimated animals however, are facing usually higher fluctuations in their environment, and it needs to be shown, whether the modification of the ion transport systems with warm acclimation might handicap an elevated ion transport needed at warm temperatures prior to molting. This may put the animal in a greater threat to predators and other environmental challenges. For this the rate of hardening of the new carapace at warm temperatures needs to be determined in future studies.

6.5 Implications for transepithelial ion transport

Overall, the total protein content in the hepatopancreas crude extract was quite comparable between different acclimation temperatures and molt stages (**Figure 11A**). However, the majority of the ion transporting proteins such as the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase are embedded in the plasma membrane (**Figure 15**). The protein content found in the membrane fraction (**Figure 11B**) did not differ significantly between stages. This indicates that no general shift between cytosolic and membrane proteins occurred with proceeding molt stages, as may be assumed from the higher demand for ion transport. Moreover, no thermal compensation of the general protein content occurred, since similar protein contents in crude extracts and membrane fractions were found at all different acclimation temperatures.

Similar to the increments in Na^+/K^+ -ATPase concentration and activity presented earlier in this thesis, Wheatly and colleagues (2007) provided evidence for generally increased protein expression of NCX and PMCA of a crayfish *Procambarus clarkii* both with mineralization cycle and cold acclimation (**Table 10**). Whereas PMCA responded more pronounced to temperature, NCX expression was more affected by molt stage, and even remained constant upon cold acclimation. From the literature it also becomes clear that the protein response depends largely on the tissue type: both the PMCA and NCX activity increased significantly during postmolt, when calcium is released from storage depots and must cross the basolateral membrane (Ahearn et al., 2004). The comparison done by Ahearn and colleagues (2004) implies that PMCA from many crustacean species and several tissues displays higher apparent affinity towards calcium than NCX, while the antiporter possesses a significant largely apparent maximal transport velocity. Therefore the authors suggested that at low intracellular calcium concentrations PMCA would predominate as the major calcium efflux carrier protein, but at higher intracellular cation activities the NCX would dominate.

Figure 15 Model of the apical-to-basolateral transcellular Ca^{2+} transport and subcellular storage in crustacean epithelial cells (gills, antennal gland and hepatopancreas) based on isolated membrane vesicles. Pharmaceutical inhibitors are shown in parentheses. SR: sarcoplasmic reticulum; ER: endoplasmic reticulum; CaBP: calcium-binding protein; CaM: calmodulin; Mit: mitochondria; Vac: vacuole; FW: freshwater; SW: seawater; and RyR: ryanodine receptor (modified image from Wheatly et al., 2002 a,b.)

Table 10 Quantitation of protein expression of a crayfish *Procambarus clarkii* in postmolt or 4°C (fold changes relative to intermolt [mineralization cycles] or 23°C [cold acclimation]) determined via Western blotting analysis. Modified from Wheatly et al., 2007.

Tissue	Gene	23°C	4°C	Intermolt	Postmolt
Kidney	NCX	1.0	0.9 ± 0.4	1.0	1.6 ± 0.6
Kidney	PMCA	1.0	3.8 ± 0.9	1.0	2.2 ± 0.7
Tail muscle	NCX	1.0	1.6 ± 0.2	1.0	3.6 ± 1.3
Tail muscle	PMCA	1.0	5.7 ± 1.2	1.0	1.7 ± 0.2

Together with the existing literature, our results suggest that not all membrane proteins regulate its concentration with changing molt stage. The NCX, PMCA as well as in this studies presented Na^+ pump are regulated both in concentration and activity with molt cycle and thermal acclimation. The almost constant membrane protein fraction indicates that most other membrane proteins remain constant, while other proteins might be regulated in an opposing way, to keep overall constant protein levels. As membrane proteins are competing for space in the membranes and the NCX and PMCA demonstrated

divergent sensitivities to temperature and molt stage, it would be interesting to study further membrane proteins to identify those with an opposing regulation pattern in order to determine their individual working mechanism and possible function during molting.

6.6 Regulation of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase function

As mentioned before, with the increased acclimation temperature, animals have less increase of the enzyme concentration within the molt stages. Such pattern matches the activity results, which indicates less increase in the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity within stages, with the increasing acclimation temperature (**double-sided arrow Figure 4**). Warmer acclimation temperature increased also the *M. magister* molt progression and therefore shorten the molt cycle (Wittmann et al., 2018). In the same line the ecdysteroid peak (molting hormone) was lowered in the lobster *Homarus americanus* (Chang and Bruce, 1980). Thus, lower Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity and concentration at 20 °C acclimation temperature reported in this study simply mirror the shorter ecdysteroid response and a faster molt cycle with shorter stage intervals. Although the general trend of protein expression and maximum activity was similar for the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase, the correlation between ln Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity and protein expression was only weak, based on individual comparisons and not statistically significant (**Figure 12**; P= 0,295; R² = 0,0405). The reason for this divergence remains obscure, although reasonable variance in the determination of both parameters and possible errors in both detection methods (enzyme assay, Western blotting) certainly contributed to the absence of a strong correlation at this level. Further work is needed to enhance the detection limits and precision of both methods for more reliable data.

In comparison, the mRNA level of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase α -subunit and ln Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity showed a positive correlation (P <0,001; R² =0,239; **Figure 13**). The mRNA expression (data provided by Dr. Wittmann, unpublished) increased with proceeding molt cycle up to stage D2. Stage D3 shows a drop in the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase mRNA level, while the activity continued to increase and reached the highest value (albeit determined in only a very limited number of specimens). This difference may thus be due to limited sample number or indicate that the changes in mRNA expression preceded the change in functional activity to some extent. A similar discrepancy between mRNA and enzyme activity were reported for the crab *Chasmagnathus granulatus*. When the crab was acclimated in 45 ppt salinity, an increase in mRNA expression of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase was found (Luquet et al., 2005) without a simultaneous increase in enzyme activity (Genovese et al., 2004). The suggested explanation was that a new Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase

might be synthesized continuously, but higher turnover rates prevented an enrichment of the final degrade simultaneously (Lucu and Flik, 1999; Therien and Blostein, 2000; Luquet et al., 2005). Besides this general correlation between activity and mRNA expression, deviations from this general pattern indicate post-transcriptional regulations, which differ between stages.

The correlation between the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase mRNA level and protein expression was weaker, but overall significant (P=0,013, **Figure 14**). Especially for the protein expression, only a limited number of specimen could be analysed due to expired tissue samples. As the data already imply a similar pattern, it appears likely that there might be a strong relationship between mRNA level of protein levels, if more specimens would have been analysed. Deviations from a strong correlation would again argue for post-transcriptional modifications and varying turnover rates of existing ATPases at least for some stages. The regulation of these mechanisms with molt stages needs further attention.

Interestingly it has been suggested that the genes for all the major Ca²⁺-transporting pathways are linked for regulatory purposes (Gao and Wheatly, 2004). An example might be the expression pattern observed for the crayfish *Procambarus clarkii* PMCA3 (plasma membrane Ca²⁺ ATPase) which directly opposes the pattern reported for SERCA, the Ca²⁺ pump located on endomembranes. The PMCA3 mRNA level expression increased in premolt and postmolt stages compared with the intermolt (Gao and Wheatly, 2004) mirroring the pattern of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase mRNA level (data provided by Dr. Wittmann – unpublished). The SERCA expression however, was highest in intermolt and decreased in both pre- and postmolt (Zhang et al., 2000; Chen et al., 2002). Thus, in crayfish *Procambarus clarkia*, PMCA and SERCA expression patterns seem to be inversely regulated. Therefore, the presented regulation patterns observed for the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase provides a good starting point for studying the regulation patterns of other transporters and their relationship to the main Na⁺ pump.

Many studies have presented temperature compensatory changes in enzymatic activity, but in only few cases it has been determined whether variations in kcat or enzyme concentration were responsible for these differences (Somero, 2004). Thus, the “quality” versus “quantity” question remains unanswered for most proteins (Somero, 2004). However, it seems to be reasonable that thermal acclimation and evolutionary adaptation to temperature may entail different strategies to adjust the level of enzymatic activity. It was suggested that evolutionary adaptation may involve alterations in protein sequence which cause compensatory adjustments in kcat, whereas acclimation may involve compensatory changes of the concentrations of proteins (Sidell, 1977; Rodnick and Sidell,

1995). In the case of this studies it seems that temperature acclimation involved compensatory regulation of the concentrations of proteins, resulted in an increase of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase relative expression, which stand behind the increase of the enzyme activity level. Switches between isoforms with different kinetic properties (K_m, k_{cat}) may be another strategy for animals living in varying environments to adapt to changing temperatures or triggers like molting. Such switches may become visible by shifts in the thermal sensitivity (Q₁₀, Arrhenius activation energy), when analysing the function at acute changing temperatures. Although some changes in thermal sensitivity between the different acclimation temperatures seem to persist, the high individual variation and low n-numbers prevented a deeper analysis on the contribution of several isoforms in molting and thermal acclimation.

6.7 Conclusions and perspectives

In the present study, protein expression levels and functional capacities of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase were analysed for the first time in the hepatopancreas of a marine Dungeness crab *Metacarcinus magister* to investigate the combined effect of temperature and molt stages on ion regulation. In more detail, maximal ATPase capacities of the Na⁺/K⁺ -ATPase and an Mg²⁺-ATPase were determined in the hepatopancreas of thermally acclimated crabs (10°, 15° and 20°C) which additionally differed by their molt stage (C, D0, D1, D2). Analysis of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase activity revealed a clear increasing pattern with increasing assay temperature for all crab acclimation temperatures, therefore supporting the Q₁₀ effect. Activities reached the highest values just prior to the molting event, thereby supporting the calcification process by facilitation of fast Ca²⁺ transport and its further deposition to the exoskeleton (Wheatly et al., 2002 a, b). The strongest increased effect was reported in 10°C acclimated animals and vanished with the increasing acclimation temperature, which indicates a dampened sensitivity for acute changing temperatures on the ATPases activity in the warmer acclimated animals (15°C, 20°C). Moreover, these data provides evidence for some thermal compensation to maintain ion homeostasis in the cold (Hochachka and Somero, 2002). Thus, thermally acclimated *M. magister* showed compensatory effects similar to what have been observed when comparing cold adapted species with lower latitudes species along latitudinal clines (Hochachka and Somero 2002; Young et al., 2006). Together, we provided evidence that molt stage has a significant effect on Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase capacities, which is additionally affected by temperature.

Within this thesis, we experienced difficulties in identifying and quantifying specific Ca²⁺-ATPases in the hepatopancreas. Non-reliable inhibition by thapsigargin prevented

an deeper investigation of SERCA. From the immunological studies, we could provide at least some evidence for the presence of the PMCA, but the final analysis of samples indicated a higher susceptibility of PMCA to degradation than Na^+/K^+ -ATPase. Thus, the activity assay needs further optimization by using the already identified inhibitors to determine reliable Ca^{2+} dependent ATPase function. As no clear evidence for Ca^{2+} -ATPase (either SERCA or PMCA) could be drawn, we decided to measure ATPase activity using the wide range P-type ATPase inhibitor vanadate in the Ca (-) ATPase assay buffer. As the ouabain inhibition under these conditions was only weak, we assigned this activity as an Mg^{2+} dependent, vanadate sensitive ATPase. The finally determined Mg^{2+} -ATPase dependent activity provided no clear pattern besides the Q10 effect. This might be associated with Mg^{2+} -ATPase specific molecular requirements, but also due to the fact that a mixture of differently responding ATPases masked the pattern. Further specification of the activity is necessary. However, the Mg^{2+} dependent activity was low in comparison to the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity, in line with the assumption that the uptake of Mg^{2+} by the animal is not that critical than a Na^+ gradient facilitated Ca^{2+} uptake, due to its higher concentration in the seawater. The quantification of respective protein expression by use of antibodies revealed some difficulties due to the presence of proteases with diverse functional mechanisms. Along with this thesis we were able to determine several inhibitors (vanadate, PMSF and soy bean trypsin inhibitor), which stabilized the hepatopancreatic extracts in a way that final quantification of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase protein expression was possible. Although vanadate interferes with the ATPase assay, this buffer optimization certainly will help to improve further development of a Ca^{2+} ATPase assay. Additionally, other tested antibodies for PMCA, F_1/F_0 -ATPase provided specific signals in the membrane fractions of at least one tissue, which may serve as a good starting point for further studies on ion-transporting ATPases in *M. magister*. The final expression analyses were somewhat handicapped by partly exhausted samples. Overall, the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase relative protein expression increased with proceeding molt cycle, and warm acclimated animals responded less than the cold-acclimated animals, in line with the general trend observed at the functional level. These increments may support the calcification process by allowing an elevated Ca^{2+} transport and further deposition in the exoskeleton and by establishing local osmotic gradients to support water influx across the epithelia to inflate the new exoskeleton. In warm acclimated animals Na^+/K^+ -ATPase responded less, both with respect to protein expression and functional capacities. Whether this compensation may help to avoid an overshoot of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase function and exhaustion of ATP at high and more frequent extreme temperatures which the crab *M. magister* may experience within its life cycle and additionally during summer needs to be shown. Lower Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity and concentration reported in this study possibly also contribute to faster molt cycle with

shorter stage intervals. Higher biological activity of the environment in the warmth puts *M. magister* in a greater threat to predators and other environmental challenges to harden the new carapace timely. Future studies need to show how the thermally compensated Na⁺ pump affects the duration of carapace hardening with temperature. Correlation analyses of enzyme function, protein expression and mRNA expression, the later data provided by Dr. Wittmann from the same samples, were done to decipher the molecular regulation mechanisms involved. Overall, the correlation between mRNA and activity was quite strong, indicating a transcriptional control of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase function. The weaker correlations between mRNA vs. protein and protein vs. activity may be caused by some methodological concerns, which may still exist in the protein expression data. However, the mRNA expression data may confirm the validity of the activity data, besides the concerns regarding high protease activity in hepatopancreas extracts. Deviations from this general pattern could be observed for some stages indicating that post-transcriptional mechanisms and protein modifications are likely involved. Alternating expression of isoforms provides another possible explanation for the divergent thermal sensitivity of the Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase upon thermal acclimation. This certainly needs further investigations with higher n-numbers and refined assays to identify the fine-tuning of this essential ion pump. Previous studies have shown that other proteins involved in calcification and intermediated storage of Ca²⁺, e.g. NCX, PMCA, increased in both concentration and activity with molt cycle and cold acclimation similar to the here presented Na pump. As the overall protein content of hepatopancreatic membrane fractions did not change largely upon the different treatments, it needs to be shown whether opposing regulation of other membrane proteins compensate for the higher protein density of transporters like Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase, NCX and PMCA.

The study provided some first evidence about molt stage and temperature dependent ATPase function and its regulation in *M. magister*. A significant interaction of these two factors seem to exist, which may affect the ability of the crab to molt in a changing climate. Further research is needed especially for the Ca²⁺ dependent ATPases in order to understand the calcification abilities and possible danger for marine crabs in the light of climate change.

7 References

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